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Housing Affordability Impacting Factors in U.S. Urban Areas from 2010 to 2020:

An Empirical Review of Theoretical Factors

By

Colby Lee Woodson

A THESIS

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Housing Affordability Impacting Factors in U.S. Urban Areas from 2010 to 2020:

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This study examines housing affordability in United States Combined Statistical Areas (CSAs) and counties from 2010 to 2020, using American Community Survey and Building Permits Survey data. It evaluates theoretical frameworks from George Galster and Kwan Ok Lee. Using a multiscalar approach, affordability is assessed through a costs-over-income ratio, incorporating both supply- and demand-side factors. A novel contribution is the integration of elder dependency rates, which limit housing turnover and exacerbate supply constraints. Findings indicate that rising full homeownership—particularly among older households—has reduced tenure mobility. The study also shows that CSAs offer a stronger analytical resolution than counties. Despite home construction rebounds in some regions between 2015 and 2020, first-time homeownership barriers persisted. These findings highlight the need to consider age composition and housing tenure in affordability research and policymaking.

Key Words: Housing Affordability, Households, Shelter Spending, Housing Units, Elder, Scale, Tenure

Table of Contents

Abstract	ii
Table of Contents	iii
List of Tables	iv
List of Figures	v
List of Maps	vi
Chapter 1: Introduction	1
Chapter 2: Literature	6
Chapter 3: Methodology	22
Chapter 4: Results	34
Chapter 5: Regions	47
Chapter 6: Conclusion	59
References	73

List of Tables

Table 4.1	Tenure Weighted Regression	36
Table 4.2	Individual Tenure Regression	37
Table 4.3	Individual Tenure Stepwise	38
Table 4.4	Correlation Coefficient Table	39
Table 5.1	North Change Regression	48
Table 5.2	South Change Regression	49
Table 5.3	West Change Regression	50
Table 5.4	North Correlation Table	51
Table 5.5	South Correlation Table	52
Table 5.6	West Correlation Table	53

List of Figures

Figure 3.1	Cost by Income Boxplots	25
Figure 3.2	Permit by Occupied Boxplots	25
Figure 3.3	Migrant by Pop. Boxplots	26
Figure 3.4	Household by Unit Boxplots	26
Figure 3.5	>1 per Room by Tenure Boxplots	27
Figure 3.6	Male by Cohort 25-54 Boxplots	27
Figure 3.7	Labor by Cohort 16-64 Boxplots	28
Figure 3.8	0-14 Cohort by Pop. 15-64 Boxplots	29
Figure 3.9	65+ Cohort by Pop. 15-64 Boxplots	29
Figure 4.1	Residuals vs. Region Plot	40
Figure 4.2	Residuals vs. Year Plot	41
Figure 4.3	Q-Q Plot of LSDV Residuals	42

List of Maps

Map	1.1	165 CSAs made of 1239 Counties	4
Map	6.1	North Spending & Owner Change	61
Map	6.2	South Spending & Owner Change	62
Map	6.3	West Spending & Owner Change	63
Map	6.4	North Permits & Youth Change	64
Map	6.5	South Permits & Youth Change	65
Map	6.6	West Permits & Youth Change	66
Map	6.7	North CSA Elder & Renter Change	67
Map	6.8	South CSA Elder & Renter Change	68
Map	6.9	West CSA Elder & Renter Change	69

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

In *Housing Affordability: A Framing, Synthesis of Research and Policy, and Future Directions* (2021), George Galster and Kwan Ok Lee provide a robust framework for conceptualizing housing affordability, bringing together perspectives on city housing and labor markets. Their analysis, based on an exploration of structural relationships, reveals the multifactor dynamics influencing housing affordability. Their theoretical review provides a crucial foundation for this thesis, as it aligns with the need to explore diverse factors affecting affordability in urban areas.

The authors identify nine key relationships that shape urban housing affordability: Labor Supply, influenced by demographics, productivity, unions, and policy; Labor Demand, shaped by technology, businesses, and major employers; Housing Supply, driven by existing housing, building technology, land availability, and construction expenses; and Housing Demand, affected by household characteristics, investment, mortgage conditions, and amenities. Also included are Household Demographics, shaped by migration trends and past affordability; Household Productivity, linked to education and agglomeration; Land Prices, determined by housing production, financing conditions, and the supply of land; Construction Prices, influenced by recent home building, construction labor, and material costs; and Market Expectations, reflecting investors' and prospective home buyers' sentiment on future home values.

Galster and Lee also offer additional theories that emphasize specific facets of housing affordability. Some theories focus on construction costs as the primary determinant, while regulatory theories argue that construction restrictions heighten costs and dampen supply. Growth theories attribute increased demand to demographic changes

and migration, whereas income inequality theories suggest that widening disparities exacerbate housing inaccessibility. Agglomeration theories propose that larger cities boost worker productivity, increasing housing demand, and induced migration theories explore how amenities attract new residents. All of the noted theories underscore the complexity of housing affordability.

This thesis examines many of these theoretical factors across different geographic scales, specifically Combined Statistical Areas (CSAs) and their constituent counties. By using a multiscale approach, the research aims to determine whether affordability factors at the CSA level hold consistent across counties or if significant variations emerge. In other words, does the broader urban context generalize across scales, or do local conditions lead to divergent challenges?

To assess affordability, the study employs the proportion of household income allocated to housing costs, incorporating both supply-side factors, such as residential construction, and demand-side factors, including demographic shifts and migration patterns. Important to consider is the use of the costs-over-income ratio, which, despite its limitations (Kutty, 2005) and critiques (Ezennia & Hoskara, 2019), remains widely used and understood. While the ratio may oversimplify affordability complexities (Jewkes & Delgadillo, 2010), it provides a practical means for measuring housing cost burdens (Joice, 2014). By utilizing this metric, the study operationalizes a multifactor analysis of housing affordability.

This research seeks to address an underrated gap in affordability frameworks by incorporating elder dependency rates into the analysis. The impact of an aging population on housing markets has been underappreciated, yet demographic shifts associated with

aging can influence affordability trends. By integrating this variable, the thesis expands the scope of traditional housing affordability research and offers insights into the evolving challenges that households face as the population ages.

With that in mind, this study explores the following research questions: What are the most impactful factors affecting housing affordability? Do the theoretical frameworks articulated by George Galster and Kwan Ok Lee yield a robust analysis of housing affordability when empirically evaluated? Which areas are most affected by housing affordability challenges?

The findings of this research extend beyond academic debates, offering data-driven insights for policymakers and households. By understanding affordability trends across different regions over the past decade, the study provides practical guidance for policy, helping to inform tailored initiatives that address the most influential factors. By taking a look at how these factors vary across regional localities, the study seeks to better inform householders' shelter spending.

For urban scholars, this research underscores the significance of geographic scale in housing studies. It demonstrates how a multifactor and multiscale analysis can highlight the dominant economic and sociological drivers shaping affordability. Future studies can build upon this approach to develop more refined models, particularly within regions that share a commuter labor force.

This study also reinforces the value of the costs-over-income ratio as a practical tool for affordability analysis. While the ratio has limitations, it enables a regressive analysis that quantifies how multiple factors interact to shape shelter spending. By

Map 1.1. 165 CSAs made of 1239 Counties

demonstrating its utility within this framework, this research highlights the ratio's flexibility in measuring the relative impacts of interconnected factors.

Ultimately, this research aims to clarify the most impactful housing affordability factors. By distinguishing between spatial scales, adding the role of dependency rates, and other affordability drivers, the study seeks to evaluate and expand upon Galster and Lee's theoretical framework through a quantitative, empirically grounded analysis.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE

Measuring Affordability

What is affordability? At its simplest, housing affordability refers to the relationship between housing costs and income, specifically the proportion of income consumed by housing expenses. Shelter is a fundamental need, and homeownership is widely recognized as essential to the long-term prosperity of households. This literature review, however, does not focus on the oft-articulated criticism of traditional measurements of housing affordability. Instead, it adopts a broad phenomenological perspective, considering the various factors that can reasonably influence the relationship between a housing unit and its residents. In doing so, the review aims to be a qualitative complement to the theories proffered by Galster and Lee, 2021.

The study of housing affordability, as a distinct contemporaneous topic of study, has roots in policy debates in the United States during the 1960s and 1970s regarding welfare distribution. Those debates centered on whether a simple threshold, based on the ratio of housing costs to income, could effectively measure need. Initially, the threshold was set at 25%, but it was raised to 30% in the 1980s (Stone, 2006). An alternative approach, favored by many scholars, is to assess affordability based on residual income—what remains after housing costs are paid. Despite the appeal of this approach, the ratio method remains the more commonly used standard, largely because it is easier to apply. Additionally, income-based methods can complicate cross-country comparisons due to differences in public welfare allocations (Heylen & Haffner, 2013). While this review acknowledges here the existence of alternative metrics, it does not focus on them, as other reviews have thoroughly explored that subject (Cai, 2017).

Aging Population

Financial security and homeownership are often viewed as synonymous. This common belief is not just a heuristic but also reflected in behavior as people age. Nearly 80% of older adults in the United States own their homes (Herbert & Molinsky, 2020). Homeownership offers more than just shelter—it acts as a financial asset that can be leveraged in times of need. Additionally, homeowners who have paid off their mortgages benefit from lower housing costs, which allows for greater purchasing power, residential stability, and the ability to modify their homes to meet changing needs as they age. Despite the potential benefits of relocating to housing better suited for older adults, many remain strongly attached to their homes, making relocation challenging. In Japan, for instance, where the population is aging rapidly, over 99% of homeowners aged 60 and older remained in their homes from 2004 to 2018 (Sumita et al., 2021). This sedentary trend highlights the relationship between homeownership and income stability among elders; financial security and familiarity are powerful anchoring factors.

Unsurprisingly, a strong correlation between homeownership and higher incomes has also been observed. In 2018, over 90% of United States adults aged 65 and older with incomes above \$75K owned their homes (Herbert & Molinsky, 2020). Yet, even among lower-income groups, home-owning older adults experienced less financial insecurity than renters. A study of 60 household surveys from 15 Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development countries (OECD) found that homeownership among older adults generally does not decline until around age 70, and even then, it decreases by only about one percentage point per year after age 75 (Chiuri & Jappelli, 2010). Furthermore, in 11 European countries, a household's primary residence made up about 80% of total

household wealth for those over the age of 65. Though that homeownership wealth yields financial benefit, it also raises concerns about housing supply for younger generations, given the disinclination of elder populations to sell their homes and their growing proportion in developed countries.

The preference for maintaining homeownership among a growing elder cohort raises the question of what connection it may have with household formation. In the United States, household formation dropped sharply after the Great Recession, with only 550,000 new households formed between 2007 and 2011, compared to 1.35 million between 2001 and 2006 (Paciorek, 2016). Simultaneously, a significant increase in young adults living with older relatives was observed, rising from 36% in 1975 to around 46% by 2015. This intergenerational cohabitation trend may reflect support for older adults as elder-dependency rates continue to grow in developed and rapidly developing countries. Additionally, declining household formation paralleled a decrease in homebuilding. Constrained housing supply and growing elder dependence leads to competitive market demand from young economic migrants and native inhabitants both in search of increasingly scarce housing options.

In response to aging populations, the United Nations Population Division proposed “replacement migration” as a potential solution (United Nations, 2001). Six scenarios were developed to estimate the number of migrants needed to maintain various demographic ratios. For Japan to sustain a working-aged to retired-aged ratio of 4.77 (estimated for 1995), projections based on United Nations estimates indicate a need for about 6 million net migrants per year from 1995 to 2000, 5 million per year from 2000 to 2025, and 16 million per year from 2025 to 2050 (Huguet, 2003). The total number of net

migrants required from 1995 to 2050 to maintain this ratio in Japan was approximated to be around 553 million. The pressure to address housing demand, the needs of an aging population, and the potential strain brought by immigration is a growing concern for many developed and rapidly developing countries.

Fertility Decisions

In the early twenty-first century, some speculated that rising human development in economically advanced countries would reverse sub-replacement fertility rates and bring them back to twentieth-century levels (Lesthaeghe, 2020). However, by 2010 to 2015, fertility rates were declining globally, both in developed and developing countries, although the reasons for these declines vary by cultural context. In Europe and North America, the drop in fertility has been linked, by some, to increasing premarital cohabitation and the delayed age of marriage—the social arrangement that has historically led to higher birth rates. Additionally, extended young-adult cohabitation with parents has been associated with postponed parenthood. A cohort fertility model from 2001, adjusted for delayed parenthood and longer recovery periods between children, predicted that most European countries would experience sub-replacement fertility, with some seeing extreme declines, said projections have since largely been realized. Though shrinking younger age cohorts may have contributed to homebuilding declines, additional housing demand persists from immigration.

A similar pattern of declining fertility, coupled with gains in life expectancy, has been observed in rapidly industrializing East Asian countries. By 2003, China, Japan, South Korea, and other East Asian nations had fertility rates below replacement level (Huguet, 2003). For example, Asia's total fertility rate fell from 5.9 children per woman

in 1950-1955 to 2.7 in 1995-2000. Singapore had the lowest total fertility rate among East Asian countries, at 1.5 children per woman in 1999. Given Singapore's low mortality and high development, one-fifth of its workforce in 2003 were temporary residents. This highlights the need for working-age immigrants in developed nations, but also raises questions about the relationship between housing supply and fertility decisions in those high-demand areas.

In Australia, a 2019 study explored how fertility intentions affected relocation during periods of high inflation (Li, 2019). Using data from the Household, Income, and Labour Dynamics in Australia survey, fertility intentions were rated on a 0 to 10 scale. Mobility—measured as the percentage of women relocating—decreased as respondents aged, but women with strong fertility intentions in all age cohorts, except the oldest, were more likely to move. Among those living in affordable areas, a 1-point increase in fertility intention was linked to a 4.36% increase in relocation likelihood, primarily to access lower housing costs and more space. However, in areas with high housing inflation, especially large cities, fertility-related relocation was less common. These areas saw lower mobility, lower fertility, and a higher median age for mothers. The Australian study seems to connote the same finding as those from Singapore, which is that highly sought labor markets are correlated with declines or delays in fertility. There is a trade-off between residing in a high demand area and starting or growing a family.

Different homeownership regimes also affect fertility decisions. A 2010 study divided OECD countries into four “homeownership regimes” based on mortgage access and the percentage of homeowners (Mulder & Billari, 2010). The study implied varying impacts on fertility rates: countries with accessible mortgages and varied homeownership

had highly variable fertility rates (1.38 to 2.06 children per woman), while in countries with scarce mortgages and accessible rental housing, fertility rates were relatively high (1.36 to 1.88). Countries where homeownership is expected and mortgages are available consistently had higher fertility rates (1.85 to 1.93). In countries with high homeownership but limited mortgage access and unreliable rental markets, fertility rates were consistently low (1.24 to 1.29). This research indicated the connection between access to affordable housing and fertility decisions, highlighting how housing policy can influence demographic trends.

Household Formation

Jobs attract workers, but worth exploring too is the connection between job insecurity's impact on home buying. A study of 1,413 economics professors in the United States found that a 1% increase in the probability of job loss decreased the likelihood of homeownership by 1.8%. This study, which used two time frames (1995-1996 and 2015-2016), identified failure to attain tenure as a proxy for job insecurity. However, homeownership is just one step in the household formation process, which also includes renting, and job security is but one factor to consider (Botsch & Morris, 2021). While a strong economy may offer job security and encourage homeownership, paradoxically robust housing markets have also been associated with increased divorce rates, which complicates the dynamics of household formation.

New households are typically formed when young adults leave their parents' homes, but divorces also create new households through the dissolution of cohabitation. A United States study from 1991 to 2010 found that a 10% increase in home prices within metropolitan areas was associated with a 3.4% rise in divorces. Home price declines had

different effects depending on household tenure, which was defined by using educational attainment as a proxy. A 10% decrease in home prices was linked to a 29.1% drop in divorce rates among homeowners, as couples waited for the housing market to rebound before separating. Meanwhile, the same decrease led to a 20.4% increase in divorce rates among renters, possibly due to affordable homeownership opportunities (Farnham et al., 2011). This suggests that the dissolution of marital cohabitation from abrupt economic change can create more demand for housing when it splits a household into two.

Exploring the impact of separation on household formation outside the United States, a study in England and Wales used data from 2007 to 2012. It found that the highest likelihood of relocation for both men and women occurred within the first four months of separation. Unmarried males were 2.9 times more likely to move after separation than married males, while unmarried females were 3.2 times more likely to relocate than their married counterparts. After separation, men and women most commonly transitioned to private renting, but separated women were twice as likely as men to move into socialized rental housing (Mikolai & Kulu, 2018). The movement from cohabitation to separation and then to individual renting is an important housing trajectory among separating adults; worth considering, too, are the trajectories of those soon to leave the nest.

Recessions provide an opportunity to observe how economic downturns affect household formation. A study using data from 1975 to 2009 found that being unemployed during a recession reduced the likelihood of young adults leaving their parents' homes by up to 11 percentage points. Of various factors, unemployment was noted as having the largest impact on this decision. Within the study's model homeownership among new

households fell by 1%, and young women were more likely to form renter households than homeowner households if they still lived with their parents by age 30 (Lee & Painter, 2013). Ultimately household formation—which inherently involves cohabitation of varying sorts—is influenced by economic factors in many ways.

Housing Markets

Housing affordability is partially determined by available housing units, and worth noting is that considerations of the broader market where pricing occurs spans multiple disciplines. In a study using construction cost data from 1985 to 2013, a minimum profitable production cost for home builders was calculated by adding land and construction costs together while factoring in a necessary profit margin (Glaeser & Gyourko, 2018). It found that United States areas with stricter regulations on homebuilding had higher housing prices. The research argues that land-use regulations create shortages in housing supply, contributing to housing price inflation. Importantly, the study notes that most of the housing wealth that has accumulated in the United States is attributable to highly sought, supply-constrained coastal markets. Older homeowners who bought when prices were low benefited the most. While younger generations now face barriers to entering high-paying labor markets due to costly housing options. Implied within the piece is that inflation in housing prices should not be viewed as a sign of a sensible market, as those rising prices are largely dictated by regulatory supply constraints.

The housing market not only has ramifications for aspiring householders, but it is also a key driver of the United States economy writ large, and its management has long-term implications for the workforce. A 2014 paper noted that the homebuilding sector

fluctuates based on production volume rather than housing prices as a commodity (Leamer, 2015). Historical data shows that 9 of the last 11 recessions were preceded by declines in residential investment. The paper goes on to suggest that central bank interest rate policies impact the timing of homebuilding booms. For example, in the early 2000s, low interest rates led to overbuilding, which later resulted in the rapid decline of construction employment, displacing 1 million workers. This emphasizes the crucial role of access to investment in fueling or damping real estate speculation and its subsequent effects on the affordability of housing.

Outside the United States, China has experienced rapid economic growth, and a study of 275 Chinese cities from 2014 to 2018 examined housing affordability using the housing cost-to-income ratio. While overall affordability remained stable, the study found that in “superstar cities,” renters spent 55% of their income on rent, and homeowners spent a staggering 120% of income on home payments. The affordability issues in these cities are attributed to land-use regulations and speculative investment driving prices higher than consumer demand. The tight housing market in these cities were observed spilling over into adjacent areas, raising housing costs there as well (Li et al., 2020). The precipitous increase in housing prices in those highly sought markets failed to balance with the income constraints faced by residents, creating severe cost burdens.

Affordability challenges differ among demographic cohorts. A study of United States tenure cohorts from 1960 to 2000 found that mortgage affordability improved from the early 1980s to the 2000s. However, retirement-aged minority homeowners in 2000 had homeownership rates 16 to 21 percentage points lower than their white counterparts. In contrast, rental affordability declined during this period. The share of renter income

spent on rent increased from 19% in 1960 to 26% in 2000, and the proportion of renters spending more than 30% of their income on rent rose from 23% to 40%. This decline in rental affordability is largely due to falling real wages among lower-income renters (Quigley & Raphael, 2004). It is important that an area's real-estate development is suited to its householders' income, which highlights the dual need for policy that addresses both wage stagnation and varied housing options.

Labor Markets

The conventional wisdom holds that jobs are the primary pull factor in attracting residents, and that income is the foundation of housing affordability. However, research suggests that labor demand alone may not be the primary driver incentivizing relocation choices. A study on "boomerang moves," where young adults return to live with their parents, found that weak local labor markets can inhibit migration from low to high-employment areas in the United States (Chan et al., 2021). Using data from 1997 to 2017, the study estimated that 11.3% of young adults moved back to their parents' home, with 52.7% of those moves to weaker labor markets. Simulated labor market shocks further showed increased boomeranging, particularly within the same metro area. The study also noted that 80% of those who move back with their parents tend to remain in the same metro area after moving out, suggesting that weak labor markets may limit broader labor reallocation. Boomerang moving to and within weak labor markets highlights the challenge of transitioning to more prosperous employment areas without external financial support.

One of the most intuitive reasons young adults return home is financial strain, due in part to credit restrictions, a constraint that is particularly acute during recessions (Lens,

2018). A study looking at the effects found that young adults experiencing credit reductions were 5% more likely to move back in with their parents. Those already cohabiting were 4% more likely to stay longer if their credit was reduced (Dettling & Hsu, 2018). For young adults experiencing a 100-point decline in credit score, the likelihood of moving back home increased to almost 3.4%, and the duration of their stay was prolonged by 9%. Those credit constraints not only complicated those young adults' departure from the familial home but may also entail shared financial obligations that hinder saving for independent living, which delays the prospect of forming new families.

The issue is compounded by declining youth labor force participation, which has been falling during the 21st century in sympathy with increased parental cohabitation. Additionally worth noting is that there are significant racial disparities in financial dependency among cohabitating young adults. A study found that non-hispanic white and asian young adults had the highest relative dependency rates (60% to 75%), while black and hispanic young adults had much lower rates (30% to 50%) (Reyes, 2022). Relative dependency was defined by income below 40% of the total household income, which connotes higher incomes among non-hispanic white and asian parents. Black young adults were 72% less likely to be relatively dependent but 40% more likely to be absolutely financially dependent compared to non-hispanic whites. Absolute financial dependency was coded as an inability to support oneself independently, which connotes not only a financial barrier to leaving parental cohabitation for black young adults, but also a need on the part of black parents for their children's income to support the household. The study argued that non-hispanic white families' intergenerational

cohabitation facilitates upward social mobility, while black and hispanic young adults face barriers in accessing the same upward mobility.

When considering labor markets within cities, neighborhood dynamics are known to play a role. A study in Denmark analyzed “deprived neighborhoods,” defined by a majority-minority population, high unemployment, high criminal prevalence, low education levels, and low average income (Boje-Kovacs et al., 2021). The study found that 50% of residents who attained employment relocated to private housing in non-deprived neighborhoods, while another 40% moved to public housing in non-deprived areas. Long-term unemployment persisted among 73% of those who stayed within deprived neighborhoods. While selective relocation from out-movers contributed modestly to the neighborhoods’ unemployment rates, the authors posit that long-term unemployment was the primary factor perpetuating deprivation. The authors offer that new construction in deprived areas might help retain newly employed residents and offset the persistence of low employment within those areas.

Disparate Outcomes

While the benefits of homeownership are well-documented, does it ensure upward mobility for future generations? In addressing that question, researchers examined intergenerational mobility between the top and bottom income quartiles within United States Commuting Zones from 1970 to 2000, focusing on the impact of homeownership segregation (Kulkarni & Malmendier, 2022). They found that the children of poor parents raised in areas with higher homeownership segregation earned 9.6% less than the median income after 15.5 years, and 12.4% less after 20 years. This suggests that homeownership segregation—along with related factors such as racial segregation, land-use regulations,

and the legacy of interstate infrastructure in creating homeowner enclaves—is an added barrier to upward mobility. Regions with more segregation in the 1970s later experienced more Fair Housing Act lawsuits and increased land-use regulations, which further reinforced existing disparities. This continued backdrop of segregation complicates the path to homeownership, further entrenching financial insecurity for those already at the bottom of the economic distribution (Lichtenstein, 2017).

Forming a household can readily spur homeownership, but trends vary across racial groups. A study using United States Census data from 1970 to 2000 showed that headship rates (households per adult population) fell by 4 percentage points for individuals in their mid-20s but increased by the same margin for those in their 30s and 40s (Haurin & Rosenthal, 2007). Though overall homeownership increased during the 1990s, ownership rates by age cohort showed little change, reflecting that the aggregate figure was largely due to the growth of older cohorts. The black headship rate—though modeled as highest for cohorts in their 20s—was accompanied by estimated homeownership rates that were the lowest among all age brackets. Though the study noted that there were differing extents to which the racial headship tendencies contributed to homeownership, the changing age demography was indicated as having the largest effect.

Separation or divorce more often than not leads to residential relocation, it is important to note the different outcomes depending on marital status and housing tenure. Interestingly, a review of six European case studies revealed that premarital cohabitation reduces the likelihood of transitioning to homeownership compared to marriage (Mikolai et al., 2020). Additionally, having children increases the likelihood of relocation, though

this effect is less pronounced in larger families. Renters generally experienced higher rates of separation than homeowners, with separated women—especially poor migrant women—facing worse outcomes in terms of relocation and financial stability.

In the United States, homeownership is intuitively associated with single-family homes, which have generally been concentrated in non-hispanic white neighborhoods. However, the market for single-family rentals has expanded, growing from 15.9% of single-family units in 2008 to 20% in 2018 (Ihlanfeldt & Yang, 2021). In Florida, a study found that increasing single-family rentals in neighborhoods where black residents were underrepresented led to a small increase in black residents—from 2% to 3%. However, this trend did not hold for hispanic residents, as increased single-family rentals in low-income neighborhoods led to a decline in their presence. Previous studies have shown that local governments have actively limited the number of single-family rentals, further affecting neighborhood demographics. The historic homogeneity of tenure options in single-family zoned housing markets illustrates how constrained single-family tenure choices may maintain neighborhood residents' reluctance to racially integrate.

Migration Effects

The dynamics of housing affordability may shape emerging migratory trends, which would seem to be an ever more influential pull factor. This review decidedly intimates the possibility that migration ebbs and flows with households' search for affordable housing options. The obvious motivating factor is the benefit of homeownership. However, elderly homeowners are often reluctant to move which dampens home-buying options. As well, household formation and young-adult labor participation have declined in sympathy with lower fertility rates, all while elder

dependency and parental cohabitation continue to rise, which seemingly exacerbates homeownership rates among young adults.

Accordingly, the need for affordable living space should be understood as a key motivator for relocation, especially for soon-to-be families, who are easily stymied by limited access to lending. Relatedly, job insecurity discourages the formation of homeowner households, and rising home prices increase divorce rates—both of which push individuals into the rental market. Increased competition for these rentals may contribute to prolonged periods of parental cohabitation, which generally discourages household formation. To top it off, the sharp decline in homebuilding after the Great Recession has exacerbated the constrained housing supply in highly sought-after destinations, creating spillover price inflation in adjacent areas (Costello, 2009).

As rental unaffordability drives some young adults back into their parents' homes, a meaningful number are relocating to labor markets with fewer economic opportunities. These weakened employment options may depress credit scores and hamper access to liquidity, which will only further young adults' delayed transition to homeownership. Non-hispanic white young adults living with parents are more likely to be financially independent while not contributing to shared housing costs, thus experiencing upward mobility at higher rates. And children from low-income households may face hardships to integration among suburban populations (Lee et al., 2012), all as single-family land-use regulations covertly maintain segregation by way of unattainable price points (Freeman & Schuetz, 2017).

Also worth highlighting is that relocation costs disproportionately affect women, particularly those moving long distances without adequate knowledge of the housing

market (Ha et al., 2021). All of these relationships may be contributing to the decline in domestic migration within high-productivity regions (Molloy et al., 2011). It is also important to emphasize that shelter spending patterns are shaped by both the internal reallocation of wealthier cohorts within the developed world and international migration from developing to developed countries (Ari et al., 2020). Taken together, the above corpus points to a tentative pessimism: many of the factors at play appear to reinforce a dynamic that will continue to depress homeownership rates among younger cohorts—thereby weakening future generations’ ability to minimize shelter costs through homeownership.

CHAPTER 3: METHODOLOGY

Data Sources

The primary data sources for this research are two well-established survey products from the United States Census Bureau. First, the American Community Survey (ACS) five-year estimates for 2010, 2015, and 2020, which provide figures for housing, household, migration, economic, and demographic characteristics at two geographic levels, those being the CSA and CSAs' constituent counties. The ACS is a useful tool for understanding the shifting makeup of United States households and trends among households. It collects data on a rolling basis and offers a series of snapshots by aggregating five years of survey data (Li & Zhang, 2022). The ACS features estimates at multiple geographic scales, and allows for analyses across time and space (Torrieri, 2014). Second, the Census Bureau's Building Permits Survey (BPS) serves as the source for derived five-year averages related to residential building permits, originally begun by the Bureau of Labor Statistics in the 1920s (Brocker & Hanes, 2014). The BPS provides insights into the supply-side dynamics of housing, specifically new residential construction. Both data sources are publicly available, enabling a meaningful degree of reproducibility.

Observation Units

A CSA is defined by the United States Office of Management and Budget (OMB) as two or more contiguous Core Based Statistical Areas (CBSAs), the CSA classification was formalized on December 7, 2000. The combining of CBSAs into a CSA is based upon their Employment Interchange Measure (EIM). Those adjacent CBSAs with an EIM ranging from 15 to 24.9 are grouped together. The EIM is based on the percentage of

workers commuting between two CBSAs, and is derived as the sum of the percentage of workers living in the smaller entity who work in the larger entity and the percentage of workers living in the larger entity who work in the smaller entity.

This research focuses on CSAs that contain at least one Metropolitan Statistical Area, as distinct from CSAs that are comprised only of Micropolitan Statistical Areas. The rationale for this focus is that many of the nation's housing units and households are concentrated in metropolitan areas, making changes in housing costs within these regions highly influential on both regional and national aggregates. During the 2010s, as the EIM between adjacent CBSAs changed, counties were merged into or out of CSAs. However, this analysis includes all the counties that were ever part of a CSA that contains a Metropolitan Statistical Area as part of that CSA for all three timeframes, with the exception of Puerto Rico's CSAs due to the island's remote locality relative to the study's continental set of observations. Creating the unified geography based on varied CSA delineations required consulting multiple reference maps (United States Census Bureau, 2009, 2013, 2015, 2018, 2020).

While one might question using all the counties that were part of these larger CSAs at different points in time—the CSA delineation is new, and a consistent geography was necessary for temporal cross-comparison. Relatedly, the OMB noted on June 28, 2010, that “the universe of combined statistical areas is heterogeneous and incomplete.” After that, public opinion was no longer required for CSA delineation, and the EIM became the sole criterion for delineation (Office of Management and Budget, 2010). As well, after that point, the naming of a CSA was based on the two principal cities with the highest populations within the CSA.

The custom aggregation of these counties for all three timeframes within this analysis is argued to be a sound approach because: (1) the concept of CSAs remains underexplored; (2) the semi-consistent application of the EIM connotes that the counties included were an influential part of the selected CSAs' commuter population at some point; and (3) given the complexity of the migration figures included within this study, focusing on select urban areas that encompass a significant portion of the nation's housing units and households provides a meaningful and manageable scope. In total, this study encompasses 1239 county and county-equivalent entities (as well as Washington D.C.), which comprise 165 CSAs located within the contiguous United States.

Dependent Variable

The dependent variable, housing costs as a percentage of household income, is calculated by weighting the county-level median shelter spending estimates (csDX) provided by the Census Bureau according to the prevalence of different householder tenures (see Figure 3.1). For instance, if 30% of households are homeowners with a corresponding cost over income ratio of 20% (csOW), 20% are mortgagors with a cost of 25% (csMG), and 50% are renters with a cost of 30% (csRT), the weighted calculation is as follows: $(0.3 * 20) + (0.2 * 25) + (0.5 * 30) = 26$. This produces a cohort-weighted median of household income consumed by housing payments, ensuring the analysis reflects the varied tenure distributions across counties and CSAs.

Independent Variables

Region is a categorical control variable that distinguishes between North, South, and West. In the regression analyses presented in Chapter Four, North serves as the reference category.

Figure 3.1. Cost by Income Boxplots 2010, 2015 & 2020, Counties Top

Figure 3.2. Permit by Occupied Boxplots 2010, 2015 & 2020, Counties Top

Figure 3.3. Migrant by Pop. Boxplots 2010, 2015 & 2020, Counties Top

Figure 3.4. Household by Unit Boxplots 2010, 2015 & 2020, Counties Top

Figure 3.5. >1 per Room by Tenure Boxplots 2010, 2015 & 2020, Counties Top

Figure 3.6. Male by Cohort 25-54 Boxplots 2010, 2015 & 2020, Counties Top

Figure 3.7. Labor by Cohort 16-64 Boxplots 2010, 2015 & 2020, Counties Top

Figure 3.8. 0-14 Cohort by Pop. 15-64 Boxplots 2010, 2015 & 2020, Counties Top

Figure 3.9. 65+ Cohort by Pop. 15-64 Boxplots 2010, 2015 & 2020, Counties Top

Year is another categorical control variable, covering 2010, 2015, and 2020. 2010 serves as the reference category in the regression analyses of Chapter Four. Additionally, Figures 3.1 through 3.9 illustrate boxplots for each of these timeframes, grouped by region.

Permits measure the proportion of building permits relative to occupied housing units. The variable prST represents the percentage of single-family building permits over occupied housing units, while prAP represents the percentage of multifamily building permits over occupied housing units (see Figure 3.2).

Migration variables capture different types of in-migration relative to the total population (see Figure 3.3). The variable imRL measures the percentage of rural in-migrants, movers from non-CSA counties to CSA counties. The variable imUR accounts for the percentage of urban in-migrants, movers between counties from different CSAs. The variable imFN represents the percentage of foreign in-migrants arriving from outside the country into CSA counties. Lastly, imIN captures the percentage of in-migrants moving between counties within a CSA, representing internal migration, also referred to as migration intensity (Rees et al., 2017).

Tenure variables assess the distribution of housing tenure types. The variable hhRT measures the percentage of renter households over total housing units. The variable hhMG accounts for the percentage of mortgagor households relative to total housing units. Lastly, hhOW represents the percentage of homeowner households over total housing units (see Figure 3.4).

Crowding variables evaluate the extent of housing overcrowding among different tenure groups. The variable rmRT measures the percentage of renter households with

more than one occupant per bedroom relative to the total number of renter households. Similarly, the variable *rmOW* captures the percentage of mortgagor and homeowner households with more than one occupant per bedroom over the total number of mortgagor and homeowner households (see Figure 3.5).

Employment variables examine labor force participation among working-age individuals (16-64 years) by racial group (white, hispanic, black) and sex (male and female). The specific variables include *WmEm* (white males), *WwEm* (white females), *HmEm* (hispanic males), *HwEm* (hispanic females), *BmEm* (black males), and *BwEm* (black females), each representing the percentage of individuals in the labor force within their respective demographic groups (see Figure 3.7).

Males variables focuses on the percentage of prime-aged males (25-54 years) within each racial group relative to the total population for each race in that age range. The variables *WmaP*, *HmaP*, and *BmaP* represent this measure for white, hispanic, and black males, respectively (see Figure 3.6).

Dependents variables measure the ratio of youth and elder dependents of each racial group to the overall total working-age population (15-64 years). The variables *WagY*, *HagY*, and *BagY* represent the percentage of youth dependents (under 15), white, hispanic, and black youth, respectively (see Figure 3.8). Similarly, *WagE*, *HagE*, and *BagE* capture the percentage of elder dependents (65 and older) of each racial group over the overall total working-age population (see Figure 3.9).

Population is represented by *ppLG*, which denotes the natural logarithm of the total population.

Analysis Method

A least-squares dummy variable (LSDV) model was applied, with the weighted shelter spending (csDX) as the primary dependent variable of interest. This model allows for the control of categorical effects across time and region, capturing the shifts in spending that aren't necessarily accounted for by the independent variables of interest. The dummy variables are interpreted as an X point difference from the excluded dummy variables. As all but one of the independent variables of interest and the dependent variable are percentage points, the effect estimates in the B column can be interpreted directly. Accordingly, a one-point increase in any independent variable corresponds with an X point change in shelter spending, csDX. In the case of the log of population (ppLG), a one percent increase in population corresponds with an X point change.

The results (see Table 4.1) feature standardized estimates under the S column, indicating how many standard deviations of shelter spending will change for a one standard deviation change in the independent variables. P-values are contained in the P column, with values lower than .100, .050, and .001, often used as benchmarks for evaluating the extent of the precision of the corresponding estimate. R^2 and adjusted R^2 estimates for how well the models fit the data are featured below the variable estimates, with fit estimates near 0 perceived as offering little predictive insight, and estimates near 1 perceived as offering much predictive insight. When the adjusted R^2 is quite a bit smaller than the R^2 , there is cause to consider that some of the independent variables are not influencing the dependent variable. As well, when comparing models that have a different number of independent variables, large changes in the adjusted R^2 may offer more insight than R^2 regarding which model fits the data better.

Within columns three and four of Table 4.1 are the results of a Backward Stepwise regression analyses. Said stepwise method starts with all the independent variables and iteratively removes those with the lowest P-values until only those that have a high degree of statistical significance remain. The stepwise results, in addition to the comprehensive regressive results for individual tenure cohorts' shelter spending (csRT, csMG, and csOW) as the dependent variable, are featured in Tables 4.2 and 4.3 and are included as exploratory points of reference.

Over-reliance on the Backward Stepwise method runs the risk of being criticized for 'P-hacking,' or focusing solely on estimates with small P-values while ignoring estimates that may be accurate but imprecise and could yield important insights about the magnitude and directionality of an applicable factor (Wasserstein & Lazar, 2016). Put differently, it can increase the chances of a regression model leading to a false positive (Amrhein et al., 2019). Important to note is that the discussion in Chapter Four regarding the regressive estimates focuses on those from the weighted shelter spending results in Table 4.1.

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS

Preliminary Findings

Several consistently statistically significant variables emerged featuring effect sizes with meaningful magnitudes, approximating around or more than .1, in absolute percentage points at the geographic scale of the county and CSA. Single-family building permits (prST) had a negative effect of about .3, highlighting potential savings from additional home buying options (see Table 4.1). Though given the positive correlations between prST and all forms of in-migration (rural; imRL, urban; imUR, foreign; imFN, and internal; imIN, see Table 4.4), it is important to consider who those cost savings are being primarily afforded to. Specifically speaking, the increased supply may be inducing demand from other localities (Vermeulen & van Ommeren, 2006). Rural in-migration, imRL, was linked to a negative effect around .1, perhaps due to in-migration from prosperous retiring rural populations moving a short distance into the CSA (Mateyka & He, 2022) given the positive correlation between imRL and prST. Foreign in-migration, imFN, was associated with a positive effect around .2 at the county scale and .5 at the CSA scale, which could be attributable to less established workers moving to a large CSA to access its labor market while opting to commute to work from another CSA county (Favilukis et al., 2019) that features more affordable housing costs. Underscoring said perception is that imFN and the natural logarithm of population, ppLG, were positively correlated. Bedroom congestion for renters (rmRT) had a positive effect around .1, which may be connected to constrained housing supply in areas with high populations, given the positive correlation between rmRT and ppLG (Jia et al., 2022). White youth dependency (WagY) was associated with a negative effect of approximately .1, which considering that

WagY was only positively correlated with internal migration, imIN, at the county scale is likely due to suburban relocation within CSAs to access home-buying options. Hispanic youth dependency (HagY), though consistently significant, did not consistently approximate to an absolute value of .1 in its effect magnitude. And noteworthy is that HagY had different effect directionalities—positive and approximating down to .0 at the county scale and negative and approximating to .2 at the CSA scale—indicating an important distinction in the housing cost burdens of counties that feature large labor markets with higher housing costs and CSAs with higher overall HagY. Put differently, distinct localities may feature varied hispanic socioeconomics (Hofmann & Reiter, 2018).

White elder dependency (WagE) approximated a positive effect size of .1, which is counterintuitive at first glance given the positive correlation between full homeownership (hhOW) and WagE. However, given the negative correlation between WagE and internal CSA migration, one likely explanation is a preference for white elders in high-cost areas to remain in their established housing unit (Iparraguirre, 2018), suggesting spatial separation in the settlement patterns of younger and older white households. The natural logarithm of population, ppLG, approximates an effect size of .3, given the logged scaling, the positive effect on shelter spending (csDX) is associated with a 1% increase in ppLG. The large effect size connotes the power of agglomeration as a strong predictor of higher housing expenses (Carpenter et al., 2018). Among the independent variables of interest, those that consistently had an approximated absolute magnitude larger than .2 between geographic scales were prST, imFN, and ppLG, as well as the prevalence of full homeowners (hhOW), but that will be discussed later in this chapter.

Table 4.1. Tenure Weighted Regression Tables

	COUNTY			CSA			COUNTY			CSA		
	S	B	P	S	B	P	S	B	P	S	B	P
Intercept	NA	31.08	.000	NA	31.39	.000	NA	30.64	.000	NA	30.00	.000
<i>Region</i>												
North	Dummy			Dummy			Dummy			Dummy		
South	-.12	-.70	.000	-.06	-.29	.124	-.12	-.70	.000	-.08	-.38	.011
West	.02	.23	.032	.08	.58	.008	.02	.24	.019	.08	.54	.003
<i>Year</i>												
2010	Dummy			Dummy			Dummy			Dummy		
2015	-.15	-.97	.000	-.26	-1.26	.000	-.15	-.97	.000	-.26	-1.26	.000
2020	-.42	-2.66	.000	-.62	-3.00	.000	-.42	-2.66	.000	-.62	-2.97	.000
<i>Permits</i>												
prST	-.06	-.29	.000	-.06	-.30	.080	-.06	-.30	.000	-.06	-.31	.031
prAP	.00	-.04	.756	.00	-.03	.928						
<i>Migration</i>												
imRL	-.03	-.07	.004	-.05	-.11	.104	-.03	-.07	.003	-.05	-.12	.050
imUR	.00	.00	.845	.09	.16	.004				.09	.16	.004
imFN	.04	.23	.000	.06	.48	.043	.04	.23	.000	.06	.46	.040
imIN	.05	.10	.000	-.01	-.02	.753	.05	.10	.000			
<i>Tenure</i>												
hhRT	.12	.04	.000	.14	.07	.000	.12	.04	.000	.13	.06	.000
hhMG	-.01	.00	.762	-.12	-.05	.010				-.13	-.05	.003
hhOW	-.57	-.25	.000	-.55	-.27	.000	-.57	-.25	.000	-.55	-.27	.000
<i>Crowding</i>												
rmRT	.07	.07	.000	.15	.13	.002	.07	.07	.000	.14	.12	.002
rmOW	.01	.03	.340	.22	.42	.000				.21	.39	.000
<i>Employment</i>												
WmEm	-.12	-.05	.000	-.08	-.05	.076	-.11	-.05	.000	-.06	-.04	.030
WwEm	-.05	-.02	.000	.04	.02	.502	-.06	-.02	.000			
HmEm	-.03	.00	.013	-.04	-.01	.212	-.02	.00	.014			
HwEm	.01	.00	.391	.04	.02	.104				.04	.02	.065
BmEm	.03	.00	.016	.04	.01	.274	.02	.00	.017			
BwEm	.00	.00	.879	-.04	-.01	.060				-.04	-.01	.054
<i>Males</i>												
WmaP	-.03	-.03	.009	-.02	-.05	.479	-.02	-.03	.013			
HmaP	-.01	.00	.554	-.13	-.07	.000				-.14	-.07	.000
BmaP	.00	.00	.712	.16	.04	.000				.15	.03	.000
<i>Dependents</i>												
WagY	-.15	-.06	.000	-.25	-.11	.000	-.14	-.06	.000	-.27	-.12	.000
HagY	.06	.03	.002	-.50	-.17	.000	.06	.03	.000	-.51	-.17	.000
BagY	-.02	-.01	.347	.15	.09	.024				.18	.11	.000
WagE	.15	.05	.000	.28	.10	.000	.15	.05	.000	.28	.10	.000
HagE	-.02	-.02	.314	.30	.30	.000				.29	.29	.000
BagE	.21	.23	.000	.05	.07	.358	.19	.22	.000			
<i>Agglomeration</i>												
ppLG	.14	.31	.000	.14	.27	.002	.14	.31	.000	.13	.26	.001
R ² :	.75			.86			.75			.85		
adj R ² :	.74			.85			.74			.85		
	FULL MODEL						BACKWARD STEPWISE					

csDX

Table 4.2. Individual Tenure Regression Tables

	COUNTY			CSA			COUNTY			CSA			COUNTY			CSA		
	S	B	P	S	B	P	S	B	P	S	B	P	S	B	P	S	B	P
Intercept	NA	47.53	.000	NA	59.87	.000	NA	30.28	.000	NA	19.75	.000	NA	15.80	.000	NA	18.06	.000
<i>Region</i>																		
North	Dummy			Dummy			Dummy			Dummy			Dummy			Dummy		
South	-.05	-.32	.021	-.10	-.45	.101	-.06	-.37	.000	.04	.19	.418	-.47	-1.81	.000	-.42	-1.26	.000
West	.02	.28	.150	.11	.76	.018	.13	1.21	.000	.17	1.35	.000	-.34	-2.16	.000	-.38	-1.71	.000
<i>Year</i>																		
2010	Dummy			Dummy			Dummy			Dummy			Dummy			Dummy		
2015	.02	.13	.280	-.03	-.15	.388	-.30	-1.86	.000	-.40	-2.22	.000	-.17	-.71	.000	-.30	-.95	.000
2020	-.19	-1.37	.000	-.35	-1.64	.000	-.64	-3.95	.000	-.81	-4.46	.000	-.50	-2.07	.000	-.75	-2.37	.000
<i>Permits</i>																		
prST	-.05	-.26	.007	-.06	-.31	.216	-.04	-.18	.005	-.03	-.15	.486	-.11	-.32	.000	-.08	-.27	.117
prAP	.00	.02	.934	.02	.17	.698	.00	-.03	.843	-.03	-.29	.438	.01	.08	.526	.08	.50	.089
<i>Migration</i>																		
imRL	.02	.05	.297	.02	.04	.706	-.06	-.14	.000	-.04	-.10	.239	-.12	-.18	.000	-.19	-.28	.000
imUR	.05	.11	.003	.23	.40	.000	-.10	-.17	.000	.03	.06	.431	-.04	-.05	.010	.01	.01	.914
imFN	.00	-.02	.814	.10	.78	.024	.11	.59	.000	.02	.21	.478	.06	.21	.000	.08	.42	.077
imLN	.05	.12	.001	.00	.00	.990	.04	.07	.002	.01	.02	.803	.07	.09	.000	-.04	-.06	.346
<i>Tenure</i>																		
hhRT	-.08	-.03	.002	-.11	-.05	.061	-.21	-.07	.000	-.06	-.03	.169	-.17	-.04	.000	.08	.02	.199
hhMG	-.06	-.02	.023	-.07	-.03	.269	-.02	-.01	.246	-.12	-.06	.020	-.16	-.03	.000	-.21	-.06	.002
hhOW	-.27	-.14	.000	-.14	-.07	.033	-.48	-.21	.000	-.46	-.26	.000	-.21	-.06	.000	-.27	-.09	.000
<i>Crowding</i>																		
rmRT	.03	.04	.068	.18	.15	.012	.12	.11	.000	.21	.21	.000	.05	.03	.005	-.09	-.05	.203
rmOW	.00	.01	.830	.21	.39	.016	.09	.22	.000	.27	.57	.000	-.04	-.06	.076	.19	.24	.033
<i>Employment</i>																		
WmEm	-.26	-.13	.000	-.54	-.31	.000	-.07	-.03	.000	.11	.08	.017	.00	.00	.946	.21	.08	.002
WwEm	-.10	-.05	.000	.13	.06	.117	-.05	-.02	.005	-.02	-.01	.743	-.05	-.01	.026	-.01	.00	.907
HmEm	-.04	-.01	.020	-.10	-.02	.042	-.02	.00	.236	.03	.01	.429	-.05	-.01	.001	-.04	-.01	.376
HwEm	.02	.00	.257	.09	.03	.018	.01	.00	.639	.03	.01	.224	.00	.00	.987	-.02	.00	.623
BmEm	.05	.01	.003	.18	.03	.001	.01	.00	.291	-.02	.00	.656	.02	.00	.306	-.05	-.01	.340
BwEm	.03	.00	.094	-.03	-.01	.451	.00	.00	.934	-.05	-.02	.072	.00	.00	.792	-.05	-.01	.146
<i>Males</i>																		
WmaP	-.11	-.17	.000	-.07	-.18	.106	.03	.03	.030	.02	.05	.630	.02	.02	.106	-.11	-.18	.018
HmaP	.01	.00	.307	-.17	-.08	.000	-.02	.00	.089	-.12	-.07	.000	-.01	.00	.452	-.15	-.05	.000
BmaP	-.02	.00	.141	.13	.03	.023	.00	.00	.908	.17	.05	.000	-.01	.00	.584	.26	.04	.000
<i>Dependents</i>																		
WagY	-.12	-.06	.000	-.22	-.10	.014	-.21	-.09	.000	-.30	-.15	.000	-.18	-.05	.000	-.19	-.05	.044
HagY	.02	.01	.500	-.56	-.19	.000	-.01	.00	.816	-.59	-.23	.000	.14	.05	.000	-.20	-.04	.116
BagY	.11	.08	.001	.59	.35	.000	-.12	-.08	.000	-.09	-.06	.192	-.15	-.06	.000	.02	.01	.858
WagE	.12	.05	.000	.07	.02	.259	.25	.09	.000	.44	.18	.000	.16	.04	.000	.45	.10	.000
HagE	-.02	-.03	.362	.30	.29	.000	.05	.06	.013	.37	.42	.000	.00	.00	.837	.30	.20	.000
BagE	.12	.16	.000	-.18	-.22	.042	.29	.32	.000	.16	.23	.011	.34	.25	.000	.24	.20	.006
<i>Agglomeration</i>																		
ppLG	.27	.71	.000	.16	.30	.020	.09	.19	.000	.15	.34	.002	.12	.18	.000	.17	.22	.012
R ² :	.36			.68			.60			.83			.45			.67		
adj R ² :	.35			.66			.60			.81			.45			.64		
	<i>csRT</i>						<i>csMG</i>						<i>csOW</i>					

FULL MODEL

Table 4.3. Individual Tenure Stepwise Tables

	COUNTY			CSA			COUNTY			CSA			COUNTY			CSA		
	S	B	P	S	B	P	S	B	P	S	B	P	S	B	P	S	B	P
Intercept	NA	47.15	.000	NA	62.21	.000	NA	30.15	.000	NA	22.85	.000	NA	16.58	.000	NA	19.55	.000
<i>Region</i>																		
North	Dummy			Dummy			Dummy			Dummy			Dummy			Dummy		
South	-.04	-.29	.037	-.12	-.55	.026	-.07	-.39	.000	.03	.14	.395	-.47	-1.81	.000	-.43	-1.30	.000
West	.03	.32	.094	.12	.81	.008	.12	1.19	.000	.17	1.29	.000	-.33	-2.15	.000	-.40	-1.77	.000
<i>Year</i>																		
2010	Dummy			Dummy			Dummy			Dummy			Dummy			Dummy		
2015	.02	.12	.299	-.02	-.10	.544	-.30	-1.86	.000	-.39	-2.17	.000	-.17	-.71	.000	-.30	-.94	.000
2020	-.19	-1.40	.000	-.34	-1.63	.000	-.64	-3.95	.000	-.80	-4.40	.000	-.50	-2.06	.000	-.74	-2.35	.000
<i>Permits</i>																		
prST	-.04	-.24	.008				-.04	-.19	.002				-.10	-.31	.000	-.10	-.33	.025
prAP										-.04	-.41	.162				.08	.55	.049
<i>Migration</i>																		
imRL							-.06	-.13	.000				-.11	-.17	.000	-.20	-.29	.000
imUR	.06	.12	.000	.21	.36	.000	-.10	-.17	.000				-.04	-.05	.008			
imFN				.10	.78	.021	.11	.60	.000				.06	.22	.000	.07	.36	.072
imIN	.05	.12	.001				.04	.07	.003				.07	.09	.000			
<i>Tenure</i>																		
hhRT	-.07	-.03	.005	-.12	-.06	.003	-.19	-.07	.000	-.06	-.03	.145	-.17	-.04	.000			
hhMG	-.06	-.02	.016	-.10	-.04	.070				-.11	-.05	.019	-.16	-.03	.000	-.24	-.07	.000
hhOW	-.27	-.14	.000	-.12	-.06	.056	-.48	-.20	.000	-.47	-.27	.000	-.21	-.06	.000	-.29	-.09	.000
<i>Crowding</i>																		
rmRT	.04	.04	.022	.18	.16	.008	.12	.11	.000	.20	.20	.000	.05	.03	.004			
rmOW				.18	.33	.032	.09	.22	.000	.29	.62	.000	-.03	-.05	.102	.13	.16	.071
<i>Employment</i>																		
WmEm	-.25	-.13	.000	-.56	-.32	.000	-.07	-.03	.000	.11	.08	.000				.18	.07	.000
WwEm	-.10	-.05	.000	.14	.07	.068	-.05	-.02	.002				-.04	-.01	.014			
HmEm	-.03	-.01	.053	-.10	-.02	.033							-.05	-.01	.000	-.07	-.01	.123
HwEm				.09	.03	.012												
BmEm	.05	.01	.006	.17	.03	.002												
BwEm	.03	.00	.045							-.05	-.02	.060				-.05	-.01	.128
<i>Males</i>																		
WmaP	-.11	-.17	.000	-.07	-.19	.069	.03	.04	.019							-.09	-.16	.033
HmaP				-.18	-.09	.000	-.02	.00	.048	-.11	-.06	.000				-.16	-.05	.000
BmaP				.12	.03	.023				.17	.04	.000				.28	.04	.000
<i>Dependents</i>																		
WagY	-.12	-.06	.000	-.25	-.11	.004	-.22	-.09	.000	-.33	-.17	.000	-.18	-.05	.000	-.22	-.06	.002
HagY				-.60	-.20	.000				-.64	-.25	.000	.13	.04	.000	-.20	-.05	.076
BagY	.11	.08	.001	.55	.33	.000	-.12	-.08	.000	-.12	-.09	.063	-.15	-.06	.000			
WagE	.12	.05	.000				.26	.09	.000	.43	.17	.000	.16	.04	.000	.41	.09	.000
HagE				.28	.28	.000	.05	.06	.002	.38	.44	.000				.26	.17	.001
BagE	.12	.16	.000	-.18	-.22	.033	.29	.32	.000	.17	.24	.008	.34	.25	.000	.24	.20	.000
<i>Agglomeration</i>																		
ppLG	.27	.71	.000	.14	.28	.011	.08	.18	.000	.15	.35	.000	.13	.19	.000	.13	.17	.007
R ² :	.36			.68			.60			.82			.45			.66		
adj R ² :	.35			.66			.60			.82			.45			.65		
	<i>csRT</i>						<i>csMG</i>						<i>csOW</i>					

BACKWARD STEPWISE

Table 4.4. Correlation Table

R	csDX	csRT	csMG	csOW	csOW	prST	prAP	imRL	imUR	imFN	imIN	hhRT	hhMG	hhOW	rmRT	rmOW	WmEm	WwEm	HmEm	HwEm	BmEm	BwEm	WmaP	HmaP	BmaP	WagY	HagY	WagE	HagE	BagE	ppLG
csDX	.72	.88	.53	.12	.14	.00	.12	.46	.07	.44	.16	-.69	.35	.18	-.01	-.02	.11	.00	.19	-.02	.08	-.25	-.15	-.43	.22	.11	-.39	.19	.06	.43	
csRT	.69	.52	.25	.06	-.01	.05	.25	.34	-.13	.22	-.24	-.24	.27	.19	-.43	-.39	-.06	-.21	.03	-.12	.00	-.12	.00	-.12	.15	.29	-.22	.21	.25	.14	
csMG	.79	.42	.56	.20	.08	-.04	-.03	.29	.03	.11	.18	-.51	.39	.25	.05	-.04	.14	.00	.11	-.07	.03	-.20	-.02	-.33	.28	-.02	-.21	.24	-.06	.37	
csOW	.55	.28	.56	-.23	-.14	-.28	-.08	.10	-.10	-.06	.15	-.17	-.04	-.02	.13	.25	-.19	.03	-.14	-.10	-.06	-.12	-.04	-.07	.02	-.06	.01	.06	-.09	.20	
prST	.01	-.02	.07	-.23	.60	.33	.21	.25	.06	-.03	-.02	.25	.32	.22	.13	.16	.39	.01	.33	.17	.03	-.07	-.06	-.19	.26	.08	-.14	.15	.05	.10	
prAP	.27	.11	.08	-.05	.32	.34	.18	.40	.20	.33	.07	-.34	.27	.14	.30	.17	.33	.20	.37	.30	.19	-.17	-.07	-.16	.18	-.08	-.21	.10	-.12	.24	
imRL	-.01	.01	-.09	-.21	.10	.16	.44	.25	.00	.17	-.21	-.07	-.07	-.12	-.04	-.05	.18	.07	.15	.04	.11	.05	.11	.09	-.10	-.05	.01	-.11	-.07	-.42	
imUR	.20	.15	-.01	-.07	.14	.27	.49	.42	-.25	.16	-.22	-.09	-.15	-.17	-.24	-.14	-.14	-.05	-.10	-.07	.09	.16	-.09	-.04	-.15	-.04	-.03	-.15	-.03	-.41	
imFN	.29	.13	.18	.05	.04	.30	.26	.40	.06	.47	-.03	-.42	.33	.22	.04	.04	.09	.06	.28	.12	.33	-.21	-.08	-.38	.28	-.08	-.37	.26	.10	.25	
imIN	.10	-.03	.07	-.06	.19	.08	.04	-.06	.10	.17	.40	-.36	-.06	-.17	.42	.21	.39	.14	.37	.34	-.12	-.04	-.27	.06	-.17	.19	-.26	-.23	.14	.48	
hhRT	.54	.28	.11	.05	.16	.42	.18	.33	.37	.00	-.03	-.52	.32	.20	.08	.05	.14	.08	.29	.16	.29	-.27	-.16	-.41	.23	.06	-.55	.15	.05	.31	
hhMG	.12	-.12	.11	.00	.30	.02	-.24	-.15	-.09	.30	-.21	-.54	-.23	-.31	.61	.62	.19	.36	.20	.17	-.05	-.10	-.03	.39	-.23	-.16	-.16	-.31	-.26	.36	
hhOW	-.70	-.26	-.41	-.15	-.24	-.40	-.02	-.23	-.29	-.25	-.53	-.45	-.12	.13	-.41	.33	-.37	-.23	-.45	-.24	-.02	.24	.30	.16	.04	-.11	.40	.14	-.04	-.54	
rmRT	.21	.15	.26	.00	.09	.12	-.04	-.05	.13	.00	.19	-.15	-.06	.87	-.09	-.31	.17	-.15	.14	.03	.32	-.27	.01	-.61	.81	-.07	-.44	.67	-.06	.31	
rmOW	.05	.07	.16	-.03	.01	.04	-.02	-.06	.15	-.04	.12	-.31	.15	.59	-.19	-.37	.06	-.17	.00	-.01	.38	-.29	.13	-.58	.89	-.12	-.44	.77	-.10	.15	
WmEm	.12	-.18	.03	.05	.19	.20	-.13	-.07	.06	.15	.07	.57	.43	-.12	-.21	.73	.46	.42	.49	.39	.00	-.17	-.24	.18	-.10	.03	-.22	-.21	-.05	.34	
WwEm	.16	-.14	.01	.15	.03	.20	-.14	-.04	-.01	.09	.15	.50	-.45	-.20	-.32	.62	.11	.58	.16	.25	.05	-.13	.05	.32	-.26	-.28	.10	-.28	-.31	.15	
HmEm	.11	-.02	.06	-.07	.17	.14	-.06	-.06	.03	.11	.10	.23	-.28	.07	-.02	.42	.18	.15	.72	.47	-.21	-.33	-.54	-.11	.05	.29	-.24	-.05	.25	.27	
HwEm	.10	-.03	.02	.03	.06	.12	-.04	.02	.05	.07	.08	.23	-.26	-.05	-.12	.26	.35	.18	.23	.17	.15	-.19	.10	.19	-.05	-.33	.11	-.02	-.31	.12	
BmEm	.25	.12	.11	.01	.17	.22	-.07	.01	.13	.08	.23	.24	-.37	.03	-.09	.41	.21	.41	.08	.51	-.19	-.47	-.62	-.16	.07	.21	-.28	.01	.18	.39	
BwEm	.19	.11	.07	.05	.08	.12	-.07	.05	.06	.07	.17	.21	-.28	-.02	-.11	.24	.24	.17	.14	.33	-.07	-.23	-.44	-.13	.02	.17	-.15	-.02	.16	.34	
WmaP	.02	-.05	.01	.01	-.08	.02	.21	.19	.14	.00	.11	-.10	.00	.05	.13	-.17	-.04	-.23	.00	-.20	.00	.02	.45	-.26	.41	-.25	-.30	.47	-.25	.01	
HmaP	-.01	.03	-.04	-.02	-.03	-.05	.06	.11	.03	.00	.03	-.07	.04	-.03	-.04	-.15	-.05	-.02	-.12	-.13	.01	.28	.28	.40	.16	.20	-.36	.12	-.29		
BmaP	-.13	-.13	-.09	-.01	-.10	-.08	.06	.04	-.01	-.01	-.10	.01	.12	-.04	.02	-.13	.08	-.23	.07	-.14	-.15	.24	.14	.24	.14	-.59	.21	.16	.55	-.40	
WagY	-.43	-.40	-.28	-.14	.07	-.21	-.05	-.24	-.31	.07	-.49	.41	.19	-.37	-.35	.23	.13	.04	.06	-.11	-.12	-.11	-.01	.13	-.67	-.32	.47	-.67	-.37	-.40	
HagY	.20	.11	.22	.03	.09	.14	-.02	.01	.21	-.04	.23	-.17	-.07	.58	.65	-.08	-.09	.07	.03	.04	.01	.00	-.08	.01	.51	-.23	-.43	.90	.20	.21	
BagY	.26	.31	.12	.08	-.02	.03	-.01	.06	.05	-.06	.27	-.24	.09	.07	.02	-.07	-.17	.03	-.18	.16	.13	.01	.04	-.26	-.53	.11	-.31	-.20	.93	.16	
WagE	-.42	-.19	-.23	-.07	-.05	-.26	.00	-.13	-.28	-.17	-.45	-.12	.43	-.28	-.12	.03	-.12	.02	-.20	-.14	-.11	.01	.14	.39	-.33	-.39	-.36	-.22	-.34		
HagE	.07	.07	.12	.03	.01	.10	-.04	-.03	.17	-.08	.09	-.28	.07	.36	.44	-.24	-.13	-.04	.01	-.07	-.10	-.10	-.05	.02	.43	.77	-.10	-.23	-.16	.17	
BagE	.16	.27	.08	.09	-.07	-.03	.03	.00	-.09	.17	-.32	.06	.04	.02	-.17	-.22	-.04	-.19	.10	.09	.02	.05	-.22	-.52	-.12	.88	-.27	-.08	.16		
ppLG	.52	.31	.26	.17	.11	.37	-.23	.08	.21	-.11	.50	.29	-.58	.15	.01	.32	.32	.18	.21	.37	.31	-.01	-.05	-.09	-.36	.21	.12	-.30	.03	-.01	

COUNTIES IN BOTTOM LEFT; COMBINED STATISTICAL AREAS IN UPPER RIGHT

Figure 4.1. Residuals vs. Region Plot

Figure 4.2. Residuals vs. Year Plot

Figure 4.3. Q-Q Plot of LSDV Residuals

Model Fits

Interestingly, even with the robust range of theoretically sound variables considered, a clear downward trend in shelter spending was evident over time. Compared to 2010, shelter spending was regressed as consuming roughly 1 percentage point less household income in 2015 and around 3 points less in 2020, both relative to 2010. This gives cause to reasonably speculate that there is another distinctly impactful factor that was not accounted for in this model, despite its high fit, with an adjusted R^2 consistently over .7 for both geographic scales, and extremely small differences from the R^2 estimates. Also worth noting is that the three regional categories for this study feature significantly large differences in shelter spending, with the South showing less shelter spending than the North, and the West showing more shelter spending than the North. The inclusion of significant regional dummy variables that estimate meaningfully large effect magnitudes lends credence to the established argument that large socioeconomic trends should be conceptualized, at least in part, by region (Rogers, 2008).

The full model for the cohort weighted median, $csDX$, does not show signs of serial or spatial autocorrelation. After charting the raw residuals by year and region at both geographic scales, the residuals largely distributed around zero (see Figures 4.1 and 4.2). Typically, positive autocorrelation distributes residuals that are all high or low, and negative autocorrelation distributes values that shift from high to low. Autocorrelation means that the residuals are correlated across time or space, suggesting an unaccounted-for interaction that may yield misleading P-values. The model estimates from Table 4.1 do not seem to suffer from an overly skewed distribution, nor a large number of outliers. This is evidenced by plotting the standardized residuals against a normal distribution in

two Q-Q Plots for both geographic scales (see Figure 4.3). In the plots, all residuals falling within two standard deviations of the mean aligned along the diagonal, indicating an appropriate level of statistical normality for the LSDV analysis.

Insofar as potential issues of collinearity are concerned, the highest correlations are found between the youth and elder dependency rates of like race. However, those correlations vary between geographic scales, suggesting that there are meaningful differences between where like racial cohorts of differing age reside within a CSA (Table 4.4). This analysis argues that regressing the dependency rates together does not suffer from collinearity due to, among other reasons, the opposing trends in youth and elder dependency rates (see Figures 3.8 and 3.9).

Important Insights

A potential explanation for this secular decline in csDX lies in the significant negative effect of homeownership (hhOW), which was not addressed at the onset of this chapter. Its effect approximated at .3 for both geographic scales (see Table 4.1). The correlative signal between spending and hhOW was negative and consistently around .7 (see Table 4.4). And perhaps most overtly noticeable is the negative standardized estimate effect for hhOW, which consistently approximated at .6—interpreted as a one standard deviation increase in hhOW being associated with a .6 standard deviation decline in csDX. No other variable consistently featured a standardized effect estimate of said relative importance. This suggests that as homeownership rates have increased while more mortgagors pay off their home loans, housing costs for those households have greatly declined, thus pulling the weighted shelter spending median downward.

Considering the rising elder dependency rates, it is likely that aging demographics are playing the primary role in this broader trend of reduced shelter spending (Brooks, 2022). This argument is bolstered by the observation of divergent trends in the decline in the proportion of mortgagor households as the proportion of homeowners has increased (see Figure 3.4). The ramification of the opposed directionalities suggests that the growing proportion of free-and-clear homeownership is yielding fewer homebuying options for potential mortgagors (Choi et al., 2019). The knock-on effect, when measuring these factors in aggregated housing affordability, would reasonably offer unintended cost savings for would-be mortgagors (Collinson, 2011), as buying a home or upgrading a household's housing consumption is stymied by ever fewer home-buying options. Put differently, households are likely spending less on housing because there simply is not enough supply to accommodate increased housing consumption in high-demand areas.

As developed economies experience significant growth in their elderly populations—and given that older adults tend to remain in their homes—factoring in the age composition of a locality is essential to understanding housing affordability, as it is hugely impactful on the amount of existing residential property that will be available for purchase by aspiring mortgagors. Another vital takeaway from the research is the clarity that was offered when understanding housing affordability trends at the scale of the CSA, which practically speaking should be thought of as an enlarged municipal area that includes more adjacent counties than the traditional metropolitan delineation offered by the Census Bureau. Despite there being far fewer observations at the scale of the CSA for consideration, 165 compared to the 1239 constituent CSA counties, the model fit that

scale more precisely, and the variability in the median estimates featured in Figures 3.1 through 3.9's boxplots centered more acutely on the boxplot medians. This is a sensible, though important, finding as it meaningfully broadens the conception of a municipality's boundaries to include adjacent counties that are connected through domestic migration and commuter labor. Put succinctly, CSAs offer a better analytical resolution for understanding housing affordability.

Another valuable revelation is the proportional disparity in-migration type between counties and CSAs (see Figure 3.3). Internal migration (imIN) is a similar, if not slightly larger, form of in-migration for counties than urban migration (imUR), but it is significantly lower at the CSA scale. So, though competition from other urbanites for housing options may affect the most people (Skeldon, 2012), competition from movers within a CSA affects more places.

CHAPTER 5: REGIONS

Augmented Models

Chapter Five features findings and analysis of regionalized regression models that are informed by those introduced in Chapter Three and estimated in Chapter Four. The prior regressions used estimates from 2010, 2015, and 2020 for all CSAs and separately for CSA constituent counties, controlling for time and region (see Table 4.1). Chapter Five's regressions separate the dataset by this study's three regions (North, South, and West), as previous regional estimates were large and significant, and the cited literature notes a regional quality to large socio-economic trends, particularly migration. The models were run at the county level, with those counties' host CSAs incorporated as dummies. Given the breadth of the estimates for the CSA dummies, as well as the intended focus of these amended models being an exploratory understanding of the relative impacts of relevant covariates, the CSA estimates are not included within Tables 5.1 through 5.3.

Additionally, the new dataset's observations comprise the delta, or change, from 2010 to 2015 and separately from 2015 to 2020. Although the augmented models using the deltas do not exhibit the same robust fit as those previously observed, it is argued here that the factors have thus far been shown to be theoretically and empirically sound (Wasserstein & Lazar, 2016), such that one can reasonably glean accurate insights regarding the effect estimates' relative magnitudes and directionalities in relation to one another's association with housing affordability.

Table 5.1. North County Change Regression Tables

	COUNTY											
	S	B	P	S	B	P	S	B	P	S	B	P
Intercept	NA	.57	.036	NA	-2.70	.000	NA	.57	.025	NA	-2.62	.000
CSA												
	<i>Dummies</i>						<i>Dummies</i>					
<i>Permits</i>												
ΔprST	.07	.26	.136	-.06	-.33	.196	.07	.26	.101	-.06	-.34	.151
ΔprAP	-.18	-.78	.000	-.03	-.18	.473	-.18	-.81	.000			
<i>Migration</i>												
ΔimRL	.10	.17	.012	.01	.01	.891	.09	.16	.013			
ΔimUR	-.03	-.04	.526	.03	.04	.491						
ΔimFN	.01	.06	.734	.01	.06	.737						
ΔimIN	.04	.06	.264	-.03	-.03	.514						
<i>Tenure</i>												
ΔhhRT	.13	.07	.012	.18	.10	.000	.13	.07	.002	.17	.09	.000
ΔhhMG	.21	.11	.000	.05	.03	.323	.21	.10	.000			
ΔhhOW	.00	.00	.965	-.19	-.11	.000				-.21	-.12	.000
<i>Crowding</i>												
ΔrmRT	.04	.02	.404	-.01	.00	.829						
ΔrmOW	-.03	-.07	.402	.10	.17	.023				.10	.18	.011
<i>Employment</i>												
ΔWmEm	-.11	-.05	.009	-.13	-.05	.004	-.12	-.05	.002	-.12	-.05	.005
ΔWwEm	-.18	-.07	.000	-.14	-.06	.001	-.17	-.07	.000	-.13	-.05	.001
ΔHmEm	-.09	-.01	.031	-.02	.00	.609	-.09	-.01	.013			
ΔHwEm	-.09	.00	.024	.05	.00	.180	-.09	.00	.013			
ΔBmEm	-.01	.00	.889	.01	.00	.819						
ΔBwEm	-.11	.00	.005	-.04	.00	.268	-.11	.00	.004			
<i>Males</i>												
ΔWmaP	-.01	-.01	.864	-.10	-.14	.036				-.09	-.13	.037
ΔHmaP	-.01	.00	.749	.01	.00	.751						
ΔBmaP	.00	.00	.943	.01	.00	.767						
<i>Dependents</i>												
ΔWagY	.21	.22	.000	-.02	-.03	.610	.21	.22	.000			
ΔHagY	-.06	-.15	.137	.05	.13	.290	-.07	-.16	.101			
ΔBagY	-.07	-.16	.104	-.03	-.09	.400	-.07	-.17	.071			
ΔWagE	.01	.00	.898	.07	.05	.130				.08	.06	.080
ΔHagE	-.03	-.12	.579	.08	.32	.077				.08	.32	.066
ΔBagE	.14	.66	.001	.06	.20	.154	.13	.62	.001	.06	.20	.134
<i>Agglomeration</i>												
ΔppLG	-.06	-1.64	.245	.08	2.61	.092	-.06	-1.67	.181	.10	2.94	.046
R ² :	.53			.51			.53			.50		
adj R ² :	.42			.40			.43			.41		
	<i>AcsDX 2015</i>			<i>AcsDX 2020</i>			<i>AcsDX 2015</i>			<i>AcsDX 2020</i>		
	FULL MODEL						BACKWARD STEPWISE					
	NORTH											

Table 5.2. South County Change Regression Tables

	COUNTY											
	S	B	P	S	B	P	S	B	P	S	B	P
Intercept	NA	.71	.097	NA	-1.36	.003	NA	.55	.000	NA	-1.35	.002
CSA												
	<i>Dummies</i>						<i>Dummies</i>					
<i>Permits</i>												
ΔprST	-.02	-.08	.514	-.09	-.29	.038				-.09	-.28	.033
ΔprAP	-.01	-.09	.684	.03	.22	.408						
<i>Migration</i>												
ΔimRL	-.01	-.01	.865	-.01	-.02	.821						
ΔimUR	.10	.14	.009	.07	.12	.051	.09	.13	.008	.07	.12	.050
ΔimFN	-.07	-.21	.051	-.05	-.16	.197	-.05	-.15	.129	-.05	-.15	.188
ΔimIN	.00	.00	.977	.05	.07	.136				.05	.07	.139
<i>Tenure</i>												
ΔhhRT	.17	.10	.000	.11	.06	.015	.14	.08	.001	.10	.06	.006
ΔhhMG	.16	.09	.001	.01	.01	.773	.19	.11	.000			
ΔhhOW	-.27	-.17	.000	-.21	-.12	.000	-.29	-.18	.000	-.23	-.13	.000
<i>Crowding</i>												
ΔrmRT	.01	.00	.807	-.01	-.01	.734						
ΔrmOW	.03	.04	.451	.05	.08	.131				.06	.08	.114
<i>Employment</i>												
ΔWmEm	-.07	-.02	.066	-.04	-.01	.447	-.06	-.02	.078			
ΔWwEm	-.10	-.03	.004	-.14	-.04	.004	-.12	-.04	.000	-.13	-.04	.004
ΔHmEm	-.06	.00	.096	.08	.01	.033				.09	.01	.027
ΔHwEm	.02	.00	.628	.01	.00	.756						
ΔBmEm	-.01	.00	.787	-.05	-.01	.165				-.06	-.01	.083
ΔBwEm	.01	.00	.716	-.09	-.01	.020				-.09	-.01	.013
<i>Males</i>												
ΔWmaP	.03	.03	.492	-.15	-.08	.031				-.19	-.11	.002
ΔHmaP	.03	.00	.331	-.10	-.01	.009				-.09	-.01	.012
ΔBmaP	-.04	.00	.331	-.02	.00	.625						
<i>Dependents</i>												
ΔWagY	.12	.12	.005	-.10	-.09	.044	.17	.17	.000	-.11	-.09	.028
ΔHagY	.11	.18	.071	-.22	-.15	.046				-.13	-.08	.085
ΔBagY	-.05	-.08	.192	.02	.04	.565						
ΔWagE	.06	.04	.130	.02	.02	.550						
ΔHagE	-.33	-.65	.000	.12	.08	.327	-.38	-.74	.000			
ΔBagE	-.12	-.27	.003	.02	.03	.732	-.10	-.21	.006			
<i>Agglomeration</i>												
ΔpLG	-.25	-5.87	.000	.12	3.01	.030	-.26	-6.14	.000	.13	3.13	.015
R ² :	.54			.48			.41			.47		
adj R ² :	.45			.37			.40			.38		
	<i>AcsDX 2015</i>			<i>AcsDX 2020</i>			<i>AcsDX 2015</i>			<i>AcsDX 2020</i>		
	FULL MODEL						BACKWARD STEPWISE					
	SOUTH											

Table 5.3. West County Change Regression Tables

	COUNTY											
	S	B	P	S	B	P	S	B	P	S	B	P
Intercept	NA	1.87	.013	NA	-3.01	.000	NA	1.79	.000	NA	-3.09	.000
CSA												
	<i>Dummies</i>						<i>Dummies</i>					
<i>Permits</i>												
ΔprST	-.17	-.57	.023	.11	.25	.379	-.19	-.61	.004			
ΔprAP	.16	.90	.020	.05	.16	.589	.15	.85	.016			
<i>Migration</i>												
ΔimRL	-.02	-.03	.817	.31	.43	.004				.29	.41	.001
ΔimUR	-.11	-.21	.171	.23	.26	.063	-.09	-.16	.184	.20	.23	.067
ΔimFN	.25	1.06	.001	.12	.39	.187	.25	1.06	.000	.11	.35	.180
ΔimIN	.16	.22	.067	-.09	-.08	.435	.11	.15	.077			
<i>Tenure</i>												
ΔhhRT	-.21	-.13	.026	.20	.10	.102	-.20	-.12	.016	.17	.08	.064
ΔhhMG	-.10	-.07	.244	.05	.02	.763	-.10	-.07	.204			
ΔhhOW	-.30	-.29	.002	.25	.12	.097	-.30	-.29	.000	.17	.08	.132
<i>Crowding</i>												
ΔrmRT	.03	.01	.734	.04	.01	.745	-.10	-.18	.086			
ΔrmOW	-.07	-.13	.315	-.04	-.04	.788						
<i>Employment</i>												
ΔWmEm	-.26	-.10	.012	-.25	-.06	.034	-.22	-.08	.008	-.24	-.06	.012
ΔWwEm	.22	.09	.010	-.11	-.03	.285	.22	.08	.003	-.11	-.03	.199
ΔHmEm	.06	.01	.450	-.09	-.01	.556						
ΔHwEm	-.06	-.01	.423	-.19	-.02	.146				-.19	-.01	.060
ΔBmEm	.06	.00	.474	-.09	.00	.521				-.12	.00	.167
ΔBwEm	-.05	.00	.521	-.11	.00	.295				-.11	.00	.191
<i>Males</i>												
ΔWmaP	-.03	-.04	.703	-.04	-.05	.756						
ΔHmaP	-.12	-.02	.155	.11	.01	.416	-.10	-.02	.107	.13	.02	.210
ΔBmaP	.07	.00	.399	.00	.00	.989						
<i>Dependents</i>												
ΔWagY	.24	.39	.004	-.04	-.03	.756	.22	.36	.002			
ΔHagY	-.02	-.03	.806	-.17	-.13	.440				-.28	-.21	.060
ΔBagY	.15	.86	.040	-.10	-.39	.309	.13	.76	.050			
ΔWagE	-.43	-.24	.000	-.17	-.06	.135	-.44	-.25	.000	-.13	-.05	.167
ΔHagE	-.04	-.08	.777	-.33	-.25	.131				-.27	-.21	.125
ΔBagE	.07	.81	.263	.06	.27	.609						
<i>Agglomeration</i>												
ΔppLG	-.51	-16.27	.000	-.14	-3.00	.397	-.49	-15.70	.000			
R ² :	.81			.56			.80			.54		
adj R ² :	.69			.30			.72			.36		
	<i>AcsDX 2015</i>			<i>csDX 2020</i>			<i>AcsDX 2015</i>			<i>AcsDX 2020</i>		
	FULL MODEL						BACKWARD STEPWISE					
	WEST											

Table 5.5. South Correlation Table

R	ΔcsDX	-12	-21	-18	-37	-04	.05	.11	-24	-47	.13	-31	-27	-31	.01	-13	-05	.04	.36	.19	-05	.28	-17	.33	-33	.33	-29	-.02
	ΔprST	-19	.54	.01	.13	.13	.00	-.08	.41	.42	.07	.10	.29	.07	.02	.10	.26	-.11	-.15	.02	.05	-.28	-.04	-.12	.27	.05	-.15	.74
	ΔprAP	-19	.62	-.08	.16	.07	-.06	-.07	.19	.34	.02	.14	.39	.04	.12	.11	.11	.10	-.01	-.06	.12	.21	-.26	-.05	.21	-.04	-.10	.43
	ΔimRL	-.25	.15	.06	.33	-.15	.15	.45	.06	.06	.19	.06	.04	.04	.26	.08	.19	.15	.06	.18	.08	.20	.07	-.13	-.11	-.14	.06	-.05
	ΔimUR	-.15	.24	.15	.10	.01	.02	.26	.22	.27	.09	.30	.29	.06	-.01	-.04	.15	.02	.05	-.10	.08	-.42	.00	-.15	.11	-.20	.05	.11
	ΔimFN	-.26	.19	.27	.14	.19	.01	-.04	.07	-.06	-.17	.22	.04	.18	-.01	.19	.08	-.27	-.26	.03	-.01	-.05	.24	.14	.04	-.21	.08	.01
	ΔimIN	-.01	.20	.12	-.03	.33	-.04	.18	.05	-.03	-.05	-.01	.20	.02	.12	.19	.15	.22	.19	.00	.09	-.16	-.05	-.09	-.15	.05	-.09	.16
	ΔhhRT	-.17	-.13	-.12	.01	.19	.02	.03	-.23	-.08	-.02	.10	.06	-.07	.10	.08	.21	.07	.22	.28	-.05	-.20	-.07	.25	-.39	.01	.03	-.02
	ΔhhMG	.46	.10	.22	-.10	-.20	-.15	-.17	.50	.15	.03	.10	.33	.37	.09	.04	.10	.17	-.22	-.15	.10	-.05	.12	-.16	.39	-.01	-.31	.49
	ΔhhOW	-.61	.05	.16	.20	.00	.34	.05	.01	-.46	.05	.18	.24	.12	.10	.04	.16	-.06	-.16	.01	.08	-.36	-.02	-.12	.23	.03	.17	.38
	ArmRT	-.10	.37	.50	.00	.11	.29	-.01	-.06	.13	-.03	-.09	-.02	-.18	-.04	-.01	-.08	-.10	.05	-.05	-.09	-.01	.43	.01	-.06	-.18	-.03	.09
	ArmOW	-.04	.15	.15	.21	.06	.21	.07	.01	-.03	-.06	.12	-.04	.16	-.12	.08	-.16	-.16	-.32	.25	.22	.21	.29	-.12	.35	-.40	.17	-.01
	ΔWmEm	.06	.17	.17	-.13	.06	.10	-.07	.10	.38	-.29	.21	.04	.23	.06	.15	.29	.42	.09	-.04	-.13	-.15	-.08	-.03	.05	-.09	-.13	.39
	ΔWwEm	-.23	-.14	-.11	.13	-.07	.05	-.21	.14	.14	.08	.15	.08	.29	.05	.36	.00	.07	-.25	-.19	.03	-.15	.10	-.03	.14	-.19	-.23	.12
	ΔHmEm	.00	.06	.05	.34	.19	.12	.10	-.09	.19	.07	.00	.22	.24	.33	.31	.31	.23	.14	.43	-.25	.02	-.13	-.07	-.12	.20	-.25	.07
	ΔHwEm	-.02	-.04	-.07	-.21	.11	-.03	.30	-.08	.05	-.05	.01	-.02	.18	-.04	-.05	.13	.06	.07	.11	-.08	-.03	-.08	.17	-.19	.04	-.26	.23
	ΔBmEm	-.04	-.01	.18	-.15	.20	.01	.26	.13	.15	-.17	-.08	-.05	.35	.04	.04	.27	-.13	.08	.22	.20	-.10	.00	-.04	-.03	-.04	-.03	.19
	ΔBwEm	.19	.03	.03	.07	.14	-.05	.14	.10	-.10	-.27	-.19	.19	-.01	-.20	-.09	.03	.23	.32	-.09	-.12	.16	-.41	-.06	-.16	.35	-.28	.06
	ΔWmaP	-.17	.10	.18	-.04	-.03	.11	.07	.08	.11	-.02	.17	.01	.19	.05	.10	-.08	.31	.20	.08	.04	.04	-.37	.20	-.33	.46	-.46	.12
	ΔHmaP	-.07	.23	.10	-.11	.06	.09	-.15	-.13	.10	.15	.19	-.04	.07	.11	.20	-.35	-.36	.46	.17	-.38	-.09	-.21	-.02	-.35	.32	.05	.09
	ΔBmaP	.16	.20	.15	-.12	.22	.01	.17	.05	.05	-.32	.01	.06	.20	-.06	-.10	.26	.34	.58	-.07	.40	.00	.03	-.07	.22	-.08	-.01	.03
	ΔWagY	.04	.03	-.12	-.13	-.05	-.02	.22	-.27	.26	-.05	-.11	-.16	.35	.04	.11	.12	.23	-.22	.49	.16	-.13	-.05	.06	-.02	.14	-.08	-.30
	ΔHagY	.19	.27	.11	-.05	.27	-.07	-.04	.04	-.05	-.17	.01	.14	-.07	-.16	-.08	-.05	-.11	.43	-.53	-.14	.39	-.47	-.04	.27	-.65	.28	-.08
	ΔBagY	-.06	-.04	.13	.05	.16	.06	-.12	-.01	.14	.03	.02	-.02	.03	.10	.31	.20	.01	-.21	-.04	.03	-.08	-.05	-.15	-.21	.12	-.19	-.11
	ΔWagE	-.12	-.30	-.34	.30	.11	-.21	-.02	-.14	-.21	.08	-.37	.03	-.38	.00	-.07	-.01	-.18	.05	-.45	-.08	-.05	-.31	.18	.08	-.40	-.04	.09
	ΔHagE	-.51	.04	.19	.05	.07	.15	.02	.17	-.06	.32	.12	-.07	.11	.17	.11	.00	.25	-.43	.50	.07	-.27	.22	-.56	.26	-.32	-.41	.19
	ΔBagE	.15	-.32	-.29	-.09	-.31	-.07	-.03	-.03	-.19	.06	-.17	.00	-.11	-.06	-.18	-.03	-.10	.20	-.29	-.25	-.06	-.09	.15	-.46	.07	-.33	-.39
	AppLG	-.28	-.07	.17	.03	.11	.11	-.03	.34	.03	.22	-.10	-.06	.13	.12	.12	.01	.40	.06	.28	-.17	.04	-.06	.00	.07	-.16	.35	-.28

SOUTH CSAs 2015 IN BOTTOM LEFT; SOUTH CSAs 2020 IN UPPER RIGHT

Interestingly, the models' fits for each region weakened from the first change to the second, with all regions featuring large negative estimates for the change in the natural logarithm of population (ΔppLG) between 2010 and 2015. One tentative explanation for the large negative estimates for ΔppLG in the first instance may be shocks to high-growth areas from the Great Recession. Another tentative explanation for the weakening fit from the first instance to the second may be the disorienting shock from the coronavirus pandemic. Put differently, as an economist might say, both instances featured different exogenous shocks—unexpected disturbances from outside the system that impacted it.

Reworded as succinctly as possible, Galster and Lee provided the conceptual basis for the selection of factors, relationships, variables, or covariates; this research, upon empirically evaluating said factors in a quantitative model, has found them to offer robust findings and insights. Now that the usefulness of these factors has been demonstrated, these amended models seek to take a closer look at the most impactful factors, region by region and between each time frame.

Regional Cases

Between 2010 and 2015 in the North, a 1% increase in population, ΔppLG , was associated with a 1.6-point decline in the weighted shelter spending delta, ΔcsDX (see Table 5.1). The highest absolute correlation with ΔppLG was with the change in the white elder dependency rate, ΔWagE , approximating negative .5 (see Table 5.4). It is likely that high-population-growth counties experienced smaller changes in ΔWagE between these time frames and that either gains in income or savings from declining housing costs were more pronounced in those areas.

A 1-point increase in the change in multi-family building permitting, $\Delta prAP$, was associated with about a .8-point decline in $\Delta csDX$. The highest absolute correlation with $\Delta prAP$ was with the change in single-family building permits, $\Delta prST$, approximating positive .7. It may well be the case that the North saw a meaningful amount of apartment construction that brought rental cost burdens down or that higher-income earners were more readily populating rentals between these two time frames (Freemark, 2023).

Between 2015 and 2020 in the North, a 1% increase in $\Delta ppLG$ was associated with a 2.6-point increase in $\Delta csDX$. The highest absolute correlation with $\Delta ppLG$ was with the change in the white youth dependency rate, $\Delta WagY$, approximating negative .4. It is likely that high-growth counties experienced greater declines in white youth dependency rates between these time frames and that either lower-income earnings or rapidly increasing housing costs were more pronounced in high-population-growth counties (Jun, 2017).

A 1-point increase in the change in $\Delta prST$ was associated with about a .3-point decline in $\Delta csDX$. The highest absolute correlation with $\Delta prST$, after $\Delta csDX$ (approximately negative .4), was with $\Delta prAP$, approximating positive .4. It may well be the case that the North shifted its focus away from multi-family permitting toward single-family permitting between these two time frames.

Between 2010 and 2015 in the South, a 1% increase in $\Delta ppLG$ was associated with a 5.9-point decline in $\Delta csDX$ (see Table 5.2). The highest absolute correlation with $\Delta ppLG$ was with the change in the black male labor participation rate, $\Delta BmEm$, approximating positive .4 (see Table 5.5). It is likely that high-population-growth

counties experienced pronounced gains in $\Delta BmEm$ and that gains in income outpaced $\Delta csDX$ (Liu, 2013).

A 1-point increase in the change in hispanic elder dependency rates, $\Delta HagE$, was associated with about a .7-point decline in $\Delta csDX$. The highest absolute correlation with $\Delta HagE$ was with the change in hispanic youth dependency rates, $\Delta HagY$, approximating negative .6. It may well be the case that the South saw a rapid decline in the growth of hispanic youths in areas with large and growing numbers of hispanic elders between these two time frames (Immergluck et al., 2016). It could be worth considering whether slowing gains in $\Delta HagY$ were linked to the previously presumed growth in $\Delta BmEm$ within high-population-growth counties (López-Sanders, 2009).

Between 2015 and 2020 in the South, a 1% increase in $\Delta ppLG$ was associated with a 3.0-point increase in $\Delta csDX$. The highest absolute correlation with $\Delta ppLG$ was with the change in $\Delta prST$, approximating positive .7. It is likely that high-population-growth counties experienced higher housing demand from home buyers and that single-family homebuilding was very receptive to market demand in those areas (Immergluck & Balan, 2018). A 1-point increase in the change in $\Delta prST$ was associated with about a .3-point decline in $\Delta csDX$. The highest absolute correlation with $\Delta prST$ after $\Delta ppLG$ was with $\Delta prAP$, approximating positive .5.

A 1-point increase in $\Delta prAP$ was associated with about a .2-point increase in $\Delta csDX$. The highest absolute correlation with $\Delta prAP$, after $\Delta ppLG$ and $\Delta prST$, was with the change in the white male labor participation rate, $\Delta WmEm$, approximating positive .4. Accordingly, it may well be the case that the South saw robust labor demand and an

active homebuilding sector that was attracting white male in-migrants purchasing homes between these two time frames (Aurand, 2014).

Between 2010 and 2015 in the West, a 1% increase in $\Delta ppLG$ was associated with a staggering 16.3-point decline in $\Delta csDX$ (see Table 5.3). The highest absolute correlation with $\Delta ppLG$ was with the change in the proportion of free-and-clear homeowners, $\Delta hhOW$, approximating positive .7 (see Table 5.6). It is likely that high-population-growth counties experienced significant cost savings for fully home-owning households. This conjecture is bolstered by the high positive correlation between $\Delta hhOW$ and the proportion of owner households with more than one resident per bedroom, $\Delta rmOW$, which approximates positive .6.

A 1-point increase in the change in foreign in-migration, $\Delta imFN$, was associated with about a 1.1-point increase in $\Delta csDX$. The highest absolute correlation with $\Delta imFN$ was with the change in the hispanic male labor participation rate, $\Delta HmEm$, approximating negative .5. It may well be the case that the West saw a substantial decline in hispanic male employment, which, out of economic necessity, led to a significant increase in additional people cohabiting in owned homes between these two time frames (Blumenberg & Wander, 2023). This, in turn, would have increased overall household income relative to unit cost. Considering that these two time frames encompass the Great Recession, this is a strong conjecture (Villarreal, 2014).

Between 2015 and 2020 in the West, a 1% increase in $\Delta ppLG$ was associated with a 3.0-point decline in $\Delta csDX$. The highest absolute correlation with $\Delta ppLG$ was with the change in $\Delta WagY$, approximating negative .7. It is likely that high-population-growth counties experienced the steepest decline in white youth.

A 1-point increase in the change in rural in-migration, ΔimRL , was associated with about a .4-point increase in ΔcsDX . The highest absolute correlation with ΔimRL was with the change in the hispanic female labor participation rate, ΔHwEm , approximating negative .6. It may well be the case that different areas in the West are seeing varied migration trends between these two time frames (Greenberg et al., 2024). As well, it is arguable that the more inland portions of the West are seeing an uptick in rural migrants that has an opposing effect on ΔHwEm (Rumore & Stoker, 2023).

CHAPTER 6: CONCLUSION

This research set out to determine which housing affordability factors were most impactful, if previously proffered theoretical frameworks were insightful, and which areas were most affected. In seeking to answer these questions, models were successfully constructed based on prior theory, offering meaningful insights into where and when certain factors are most operative, or most closely related, to household shelter spending. This piece will now conclude by emphasizing some of its most distinctly important and novel scholarly contributions: most notably, elevating the focus on the growing role of elder dependency rates—most acutely non-hispanic white elder dependency rates (see Figure 3.9)—in shaping trends in shelter spending and homeownership.

Another key contribution is demonstrating that CSAs provide a stronger analytical resolution for housing affordability than counties alone. By incorporating broadened urban commuting zones within regional labor markets, it reveals that affordability trends observed at the county level obscure larger dynamics, particularly migration-driven demand and the distribution of homeownership.

Between 2010 and 2015, the proportion of free-and-clear homeowners grew significantly across most CSAs (see Maps 6.1 through 6.3). Between 2015 and 2020, that growth became even more pronounced. Regardless of region, increasing rates of full homeownership were observed across the studied time frames. Unsurprisingly—given (a) the substantial cost savings from paying off a mortgage, (b) the inclusion of all household cohorts in the cohort-weighted shelter spending median, and (c) the secular increase in homeownership—a concurrent decline in the aggregate measure of housing affordability can be observed, beginning in the first period and intensifying in the second. Those

increases in full homeownership were met with declines among mortgagors, showing a tenure bottleneck locking up turnover of existing residential real estate, thus intensifying challenges for first-time homebuyers (see Figure 3.4).

Though this trend was widespread in both periods and most pronounced in the second, it was most widespread in the North during the first. This region saw higher and more evenly distributed increases in non-hispanic white elder dependency rates. With the marked decline in homebuilding following the Great Recession (see Figure 3.2), combined with the ascent of elders who prefer to age in place, a significant spike in renter households was observed between 2010 and 2015 across all regions (see Maps 6.7 through 6.9). This trend reversed slightly in the South and West between 2015 and 2020, but rentership continued to grow in the North, albeit at a reduced rate. And housing demand, particularly in-migration, behaved differently across geographic scales—while suburban counties within CSAs seemingly absorbed relocating homebuyers seeking affordable supply, urban core counties (e.g., higher-population counties) presumably remained primary rental markets. This divergence underscores the benefit of a multiscale approach in understanding the push-and-pull factors shaping housing affordability.

The decline and subsequent rebound in single-family housing construction—units most commonly associated with child-rearing—was mild in the North but pronounced in the South and West. However, despite this rebound in single-family homebuilding in the second period, the decline in non-hispanic white youth dependency rates observed in the first period persisted into the second (see Maps 6.4 through 6.6). These declines were concurrent with only small gains in hispanic youth dependency rates and slight declines

Map 6.3. West CSA Spending & Owner Change Map

Map 6.4. North CSA Permits & Youth Change Map

Map 6.5. South CSA Permits & Youth Change Map

Map 6.6. West CSA Permits & Youth Change Map

Map 6.7. North CSA Elder & Renter Change Map

Map 6.8. South CSA Elder & Renter Change Map

Map 6.9. West CSA Elder & Renter Change Map

in black youth dependency rates (see Figure 3.8). This largely sustained downturn in youth dependency, despite renewed home construction, suggests that sluggish homebuilding alone does not fully explain barriers to homeownership among younger buyers. Instead, the combination of an aging homeowner base that remains in place and the slow resupply of available home-buying options seems to inhibit the transition into first-time homeownership.

All that said, if one were to attempt a historiography of the recent decade seen through the lens of housing affordability, it might go as follows: Millennials—those born between 1981 and 1996, often characterized by delayed homeownership, economic precarity, and higher rates of renting—attempted to take flight from the parental nest just as homebuilding plummeted and job prospects dwindled (see Figure 3.7). Consequently, they flocked to rentals or back to the nest (Fry, 2013), all while Baby Boomers held on to their vocations due to economic anxiety (Rosenstiel, 2009). Then, just as Millennials were prepping for a second attempt at departing the launch pad, the coronavirus pandemic triggered a silver tsunami of newly retired (Faria-e-Castro, 2021), home-equity-rich Baby Boomers flooding into the supply-constrained housing market. This surge drove home prices beyond the reach of otherwise would-be first-time homebuyers (National Association of Realtors, 2024), further delaying family formation.

That account is somewhat verbose, but it is intended to emphasize a crucial point: the growing proportion of older homeowners in United States metropolitan areas—specifically the studied CSAs—has not only been the dominant force shaping housing trends, but it is intensifying too. Therefore, urban planning trends such as cost-prohibitive forms of New Urbanism—e.g., walkable neighborhoods and mixed-use developments

(Talen, 2010)—or ambitious transit-oriented development that fail to meaningfully address housing consumption by older homeowners miss the big picture. Restated with a more academic tone, as full homeownership continues to rise among older generations, the housing market remains structurally constrained—not only by limited turnover but also by induced migration patterns that reinforce affordability pressures. Younger households most affected by rising costs are seemingly funneled into rentals, while existing real-estate markets absorb older, financially secure buyers, further restricting the supply of starter homes. This dynamic entrenches intergenerational wealth gaps, as home equity remains concentrated among older households, limiting pathways to ownership for younger generations. Without policies that address these patterns of tenure and immobility, affordability challenges could persist beyond cyclical fluctuations.

Given the deleterious effects of concentrated homeownership among the elderly on younger generations' ability to access and accumulate home equity, policymakers should be cautious about incentivizing aging in place (Ferreira, 2004). Specifically, “homestead exemptions”—targeted property tax abatements designed to reduce the tax burden on primarily older homeowners—in various forms have been implemented across multiple states, including Florida's Save Our Homes Amendment, New York's School Tax Relief Program, Texas's Appraisal Cap, Oregon's Measure 50, Georgia's Floating Homestead Exemption, Illinois' Senior Freeze Exemption, California's Proposition 13, and so on. These policies aim to limit tax increases or cap assessments, benefiting existing homeowners with housing cost reductions. However, they advantage established homeowners while creating generational disparities, shifting some of the property tax burden onto newer, younger buyers, who pay relatively higher taxes. By locking in long-

term owners with lower tax rates, these policies can discourage housing turnover, reinforcing inequality by restricting access for aspiring homeowners (Stohs et al., 2001). Moreover, in some instances, such subsidies have made housing less affordable, as the financial benefits become factored into home values in areas with high recipient concentrations (Moulton et al., 2018). Though intended to prevent the displacement of low-income homeowners, these abatements have been observed to primarily benefit wealthier seniors (Kim & Dawkins, 2021), effectively serving as a wealth preservation tool for high-value property owners (Allen & Dare, 2009). Ultimately, by reducing housing market turnover, these tax policies can contribute to housing supply shortages and affordability challenges for new families.

References

- Allen, M., & Dare, W. (2009). Changes in Property Tax Progressivity for Florida Homeowners after the “Save Our Homes Amendment.” *Journal of Real Estate Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10835547.2009.12091232>
- Amrhein, V., Greenland, S., & McShane, B. (2019). Scientists rise up against statistical significance. *Nature*. <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-019-00857-9>
- Ari, A., Puy, D., & Shi, Y. (2020). *Foreign Demand and Local House Prices: Evidence from the US*. International Monetary Fund.
https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3583405
- Aurand, A. (2014). Florida’s Planning Requirements and Affordability for Low-Income Households. *Housing Studies*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02673037.2014.882497>
- Blumenberg, E., & Wander, M. (2023). Housing affordability and commute distance. *Urban Geography*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02723638.2022.2087319>
- Boje-Kovacs, B., Egsgaard-Pedersen, A., & Weatherall, C. (2021). Residential mobility and persistent neighborhood deprivation. *Journal of Housing Economics*.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhe.2021.101771>
- Botsch, M., & Morris, S. (2021). Job loss risk, expected mobility, and home ownership. *Journal of Housing Economics*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhe.2020.101733>
- Brocker, M., & Hanes, C. (2014). *The 1920s American Real Estate Boom and the Downturn of the Great Depression*. National Bureau of Economic Research.
<https://ssrn.com/abstract=2226820>

- Brooks, M. (2022). The Changing Landscape of Affordable Housing in the Rural and Urban United States, 1990–2016. *Rural Sociology*.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/ruso.12427>
- Cai, Z. (2017). *Analyzing measurements of housing affordability*. University of Washington. <https://digital.lib.washington.edu/researchworks/items/cddc05e3-e514-4c8f-ba5a-ef34eb091b44/full>
- Carpenter, A., White, D., & Hirt, M. (2018). *Rental Housing Affordability in the Southeast: Data from the Sixth District*. Federal Reserve Bank of Atlanta, Community and Economic Development. <https://doi.org/10.29338/dp2018-02>
- Chan, S., O'Regan, K., & You, W. (2021). Migration choices of the boomerang generation: Does returning home dampen labor market adjustment? *Journal of Housing Economics*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhe.2021.101760>
- Chiuri, M., & Jappelli, T. (2010). Do the elderly reduce housing equity? An international comparison. *Journal of Population Economics*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00148-008-0217-4>
- Choi, J., Goodman, L., Zhu, J., & Walsh, J. (2019). *Senior Housing and Mobility: Recent Trends and Implications for the Housing Market*. Urban Institute.
<https://www.urban.org/research/publication/senior-housing-and-mobility-recent-trends-and-implications-housing-market>
- Collinson, R. (2011). Rental Housing Affordability Dynamics, 1990-2009. *Cityscape: A Journal of Policy Development and Research*.
<https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1914505>

- Costello, L. (2009). Urban–Rural Migration: Housing availability and affordability. *Australian Geographer*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00049180902974776>
- Dettling, L., & Hsu, J. (2018). Returning to the nest: Debt and parental co-residence among young adults. *Labour Economics*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.labeco.2017.12.006>
- Faria-e-Castro, M. (2021). “Excess” retirements during the COVID-19 pandemic. Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis, On the Economy. <https://www.stlouisfed.org/on-the-economy/2021/december/excess-retirements-covid-19-pandemic>
- Farnham, M., Schmidt, L., & Sevak, P. (2011). House Prices and Marital Stability. *American Economic Review*. <https://doi.org/10.1257/aer.101.3.615>
- Favilukis, J., Mabile, P., & Van Nieuwerburgh, S. (2019). *Affordable Housing and City Welfare*. National Bureau of Economic Research. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w25906>
- Ferreira, F. (2004). *You Can Take It with You: Transferability of Proposition 13 Tax Benefits, Residential Mobility, and Willingness to Pay for Housing Amenities*. Center for Labor Economics. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.661421>
- Freeman, L., & Schuetz, J. (2017). Producing Affordable Housing in Rising Markets: What Works? *Cityscape: A Journal of Policy Development and Research*. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26328307>
- Freemark, Y. (2023). Zoning Change: Upzonings, Downzonings, and Their Impacts on Residential Construction, Housing Costs, and Neighborhood Demographics. *Journal of Planning Literature*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/08854122231166961>

- Fry, R. (2013). *A rising share of young adults live in their parents' home*. Pew Research Center. <https://www.pewresearch.org/social-trends/2013/08/01/a-rising-share-of-young-adults-live-in-their-parents-home/>
- Galster, G., & Lee, K. (2021). Housing affordability: A framing, synthesis of research and policy, and future directions. *International Journal of Urban Sciences*.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/12265934.2020.1713864>
- Glaeser, E., & Gyourko, J. (2018). The Economic Implications of Housing Supply. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*. <https://doi.org/10.1257/jep.32.1.3>
- Greenberg, M., Angelo, H., Losada, E., & Wilmers, C. (2024). *Relational geographies of urban unsustainability: The entanglement of California's housing crisis with WUI growth and climate change*. Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences.
<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2310080121>
- Ha, S., Hilber, C., & Schöni, O. (2021). Do long-distance moves discourage homeownership? Evidence from England. *Journal of Housing Economics*.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhe.2021.101766>
- Haurin, D., & Rosenthal, S. (2007). The Influence of Household Formation on Homeownership Rates Across Time and Race. *Real Estate Economics*.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6229.2007.00196.x>
- Herbert, C., & Molinsky, J. (2020). Homeownership Among Older Adults: A Source of Stability—Or Stress? *Generations Journal*.
<https://generations.asaging.org/homeownership-older-adults-stability-stress>

- Heylen, K., & Haffner, M. (2013). A ratio or budget benchmark for comparing affordability across countries? *Journal of Housing and the Built Environment*.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10901-012-9325-2>
- Hofmann, E., & Reiter, E. (2018). Geographic Variation in Sex Ratios of the US Immigrant Population: Identifying Sources of Difference. *Population Research and Policy Review*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11113-018-9469-1>
- Huguet, J. (2003). Can migration avert population decline and ageing in East and Southeast Asia? *Journal of Population Research*.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/BF03031798>
- Ihlanfeldt, K., & Yang, C. (2021). Single-family rentals and neighborhood racial integration. *Journal of Housing Economics*.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhe.2021.101780>
- Immergluck, D., & Balan, T. (2018). Sustainable for whom? Green urban development, environmental gentrification, and the Atlanta Beltline. *Urban Geography*.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/02723638.2017.1360041>
- Immergluck, D., Carpenter, A., & Lueders, A. (2016). *Declines in Low-Cost Rented Housing Units in Eight Large Southeastern Cities*. Federal Reserve Bank of Atlanta, Community and Economic Development.
https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2782762
- Iparraguirre, J. (2018). *Economics and Ageing: Volume I: Theory*. Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-93248-4>

- Jewkes, M., & Delgadillo, L. (2010). Weaknesses of Housing Affordability Indices Used by Practitioners. *Journal of Financial Counseling and Planning*.
<https://ssrn.com/abstract=2222052>
- Jia, N., Molloy, R., Smith, C., & Wozniak, A. (2022). *The Economics of Internal Migration: Advances and Policy Questions*. Board of Governors of the Federal Reserve System, Finance and Economics.
<https://doi.org/10.17016/FEDS.2022.003>
- Joice, P. (2014). Measuring Housing Affordability. *Cityscape: A Journal of Policy Development and Research*. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26326872>
- Jun, H. (2017). The Link Between Local Comprehensive Plans and Housing Affordability: A Comparative Study of the Atlanta and Detroit Metropolitan Areas. *Journal of the American Planning Association*.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/01944363.2017.1321496>
- Kim, J., & Dawkins, C. (2021). Aging, Property Taxes, and Housing Adjustments: Lessons From the Health and Retirement Study. *Housing Policy Debate*.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10511482.2021.1887319>
- Kulkarni, N., & Malmendier, U. (2022). Homeownership segregation. *Journal of Monetary Economics*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmoneco.2022.05.001>
- Kutty, N. (2005). A new measure of housing affordability: Estimates and analytical results. *Housing Policy Debate*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10511482.2005.9521536>
- Leamer, E. (2015). Housing Really Is the Business Cycle: What Survives the Lessons of 2008-09? *Journal of Money, Credit and Banking*.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/jmcb.12189>

- Lee, K., & Painter, G. (2013). What happens to household formation in a recession? *Journal of Urban Economics*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jue.2013.03.004>
- Lee, S., Parrott, K., & Ahn, M. (2012). Exploring Housing Challenges of Low-Income Minority Populations in the Southern United States. *Cityscape: A Journal of Policy Development and Research*. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/41553082>
- Lens, M. (2018). Extremely low-income households, housing affordability and the Great Recession. *Urban Studies*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0042098016686511>
- Lesthaeghe, R. (2020). The second demographic transition, 1986–2020: Sub-replacement fertility and rising cohabitation—a global update. *Genus*. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41118-020-00077-4>
- Li, A. (2019). Fertility intention-induced relocation: The mediating role of housing markets. *Population, Space and Place*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/psp.2265>
- Li, K., Qin, Y., & Wu, J. (2020). Recent housing affordability in urban China: A comprehensive overview. *China Economic Review*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chieco.2019.101362>
- Li, Y., & Zhang, S. (2022). *Applied Research Methods in Urban and Regional Planning*. Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-93574-0>
- Lichtenstein, B. (2017). Debt, death, and divorce: aging into foreclosure in the U.S. Deep South. *Housing and Society*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08882746.2017.1378051>
- Liu, C. (2013). Latino Immigration and the Low-Skill Urban Labor Market: The Case of Atlanta. *Social Science Quarterly*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6237.2012.00858.x>

- López-Sanders, L. (2009). *Trapped at the Bottom: Racialized and Gendered Labor Queues in New Immigrant Destinations*. Center for Comparative Immigration Studies. https://ccis.ucsd.edu/_files/wp176.pdf
- Mateyka, P., & He, W. (2022). *Domestic Migration of Older Americans 2015-2019*. United States Census Bureau. <https://www.census.gov/content/dam/Census/library/publications/2022/demo/p23-218.pdf>
- Mikolai, J., & Kulu, H. (2018). Short- and long-term effects of divorce and separation on housing tenure in England and Wales. *Population Studies*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00324728.2017.1391955>
- Mikolai, J., Kulu, H., & Mulder, C. (2020). Family life transitions, residential relocations, and housing in the life course. *Demographic Research*. <https://doi.org/10.4054/DemRes.2020.43.2>
- Molloy, R., Smith, C., & Wozniak, A. (2011). Internal Migration in the United States. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*. <https://doi.org/10.1257/jep.25.3.173>
- Moulton, J., Waller, B., & Wentland, S. (2018). Who Benefits from Targeted Property Tax Relief? Evidence from Virginia Elections. *Journal of Policy Analysis and Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pam.22054>
- Mulder, C., & Billari, F. (2010). Homeownership Regimes and Low Fertility. *Housing Studies*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02673031003711469>
- National Association of Realtors. (2024). *2024 profile of home buyers and sellers: Highlights*. National Association of Realtors.

https://www.nar.realtor/sites/default/files/2024-11/2024-profile-of-home-buyers-and-sellers-highlights-11-04-2024_2.pdf

Office of Management and Budget. (2010). *2010 Standards for delineating metropolitan and micropolitan statistical areas: Notice of decision*. Office of Management and Budget. <https://www.govinfo.gov/content/pkg/FR-2010-06-28/pdf/2010-15605.pdf>

Paciorek, A. (2016). The Long and the Short of Household Formation. *Real Estate Economics*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1540-6229.12085>

Quigley, J., & Raphael, S. (2004). Is Housing Unaffordable? Why Isn't It More Affordable? *Journal of Economic Perspectives*. <https://doi.org/10.1257/089533004773563494>

Rees, P., Bell, M., Kupiszewski, M., Kupiszewska, D., Ueffing, P., Bernard, A., Charles-Edwards, E., & Stillwell, J. (2017). The Impact of Internal Migration on Population Redistribution. *Population, Space and Place*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/psp.2036>

Reyes, A. (2022). Race and Ethnic Differences in Financial Dependency of Coresident Young Adults During Economic Recessions and Over Time. *Journal of Family and Economic Issues*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10834-021-09762-8>

Rogers, A. (2008). Demographic Modeling of the Geography of Migration and Population: A Multiregional Perspective. *Geographical Analysis*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1538-4632.2008.00726.x>

- Rosenstiel, T. (2009). *Recession turns a graying office grayer*. Pew Research Center.
<https://www.pewresearch.org/social-trends/2009/09/03/recession-turns-a-graying-office-grayer/>
- Rumore, D., & Stoker, P. (2023). *Rural Gentrification and the Spillover Effect: Integrated Transportation, Housing, and Land Use Challenges and Strategies in Gateway Communities*. Transportation Research and Education Center.
<https://doi.org/10.15760/trec.287>
- Skeldon, R. (2012). Migration Transitions Revisited: Their Continued Relevance for The Development of Migration Theory. *Population, Space and Place*.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/psp.667>
- Stephen Ezennia, I., & Hoskara, S. (2019). Methodological weaknesses in the measurement approaches and concept of housing affordability used in housing research: A qualitative study. *Plos One*.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0221246>
- Stohs, M., Childs, P., & Stevenson, S. (2001). Tax Policies and Residential Mobility. *International Real Estate Review*. <https://doi.org/10.53383/100031>
- Stone, M. (2006). What is housing affordability? The case for the residual income approach. *Housing Policy Debate*.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10511482.2006.9521564>
- Sumita, K., Nakazawa, K., & Kawase, A. (2021). Long-term care facilities and migration of elderly households in an aged society: Empirical analysis based on micro data. *Journal of Housing Economics*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhe.2021.101770>

Talen, E. (2010). Affordability in New Urbanist development: Principle, practice, and strategy. *Journal of Urban Affairs*. [https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9906.2010.00518.x)

[9906.2010.00518.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9906.2010.00518.x)

Torrieri, N. (2014). *American Community Survey Design and Methodology*. United States Census Bureau. <https://www2.census.gov/library/publications/2014/acs/acs-design-methodology.pdf>

United Nations. (2001). *Replacement migration: Is it a solution to declining and ageing populations?* United Nations Secretariat, Population Division.

<https://hdl.loc.gov/loc.gdc/gdcebookspublic.2021762789>

United States Census Bureau. (2009). *Combined Statistical Areas of the United States and Puerto Rico*. United States Department of Commerce.

https://www2.census.gov/geo/maps/metroarea/us_wall/Dec_2009/csa_us_1209.pdf

United States Census Bureau. (2013). *Combined Statistical Areas of the United States and Puerto Rico*. United States Department of Commerce.

https://www2.census.gov/geo/maps/metroarea/us_wall/Feb2013/csa_us_0213.pdf

United States Census Bureau. (2015). *Combined Statistical Areas of the United States and Puerto Rico*. United States Department of Commerce.

https://www2.census.gov/geo/maps/metroarea/us_wall/Jul2015/csa_us_0715.pdf

United States Census Bureau. (2018). *Combined Statistical Areas of the United States and Puerto Rico*. United States Department of Commerce.

https://www2.census.gov/geo/maps/metroarea/us_wall/Sep2018/CSA_WallMap_Sep2018.pdf

- United States Census Bureau. (2020). *Combined Statistical Areas of the United States and Puerto Rico*. United States Department of Commerce.
https://www2.census.gov/geo/maps/metroarea/us_wall/Mar2020/CSA_WallMap_Mar2020.pdf
- Vermeulen, W., & van Ommeren, J. (2006). *Housing supply and the interaction of regional population and employment*. Netherlands Bureau for Economic Policy Analysis. <https://www.cpb.nl/sites/default/files/publicaties/download/housing-supply-and-interaction-regional-population-and-employment.pdf>
- Villarreal, A. (2014). Explaining the Decline in Mexico-U.S. Migration: The Effect of the Great Recession. *Demography*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13524-014-0351-4>
- Wasserstein, R., & Lazar, N. (2016). The ASA Statement on p -Values: Context, Process, and Purpose. *The American Statistician*.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00031305.2016.1154108>